

Innovative noise modelling

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Responsible authors	Calvin Jephcote & John Gulliver	
E-mail / phone responsible authors	cj191@leicester.ac.uk	jgullive@sgul.ac.uk

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2. Introduction

This report focusses on the implementation of the CNOSOS noise prediction methodology within the Equal-Life project. The intention of this document is to provide an overview of the metrics and data required in the context of open-source applications (i.e. harmonised between countries), including open street maps (OSM), meteorological data, and land cover. This principle extends to implementation of the modelling in freely available software. The intention is to provide an approach which accessible to all areas of interest in the Equal-Life project and the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) of projects. An aspect of the innovation in noise modelling here is providing a user-friendly account of the approach to noise modelling in an epidemiologic context via open data where possible.

For a technical description of sound power emissions and free-field propagation we refer the reader to the comprehensive methodology published elsewhere. D3.4 is supplemented (Appendix) with the scripts that can be used to apply the pre-processing and noise modelling for exposure assessment.

Innovation extends to an assessment of the minimum, maximum, and variability in A-weighted noise levels around facades of dwellings. We also refer to other deliverables where we absorb data on traffic count estimates (D3.2) and new models and metrics for the exposome (D3.5). There is also presentation of how traffic count estimates are extrapolated over time for the UK data. For other countries, the traffic flows (D3.2) and noise estimates presented here are nominally for the year 2019. We will scale the outputs to other years based on the needs of the cohorts.

This report includes an exemplar application for the ALSPAC cohort in the UK in detail and modelling results from model application in three other cohorts (BREATHE and WALNUTS in Spain, and STARS in Sweden). Here we use traffic estimations on major (conventional approach in line with strategic noise mapping; e.g. European Noise Directive) and minor roads (based on modelled estimates, following the method presented in D3.2). Thus, the density of traffic flows is superior to standard applications for noise modelling. Some of the geographical datasets used in this specific example were under licence from the UK mapping agency (Ordnance Survey), due to the prior work done for ALSPAC on developing a GIS for multiple exposure generation. The same principles described in this report for using OSM data for road geography, buildings and landcover. We describe how to generate data outside for open modelling as per the application to the cohorts in Spain and Sweden.

3. Method for modelling road-transport noise estimates

Modelled road-transport noise estimates are calculated using the 'Common framework for noise assessment methods' (CNOSSOS-EU), developed in accordance with European Commission Directive 2002/49/EC (Kephelopoulos et al 2012).

Researchers at the University of Leicester have implemented the CNOSSOS-EU model algorithms in PostgreSQL via the PostGIS v2.1 extension, following the protocol described by Morley et al (2015). The model requires:

- Annual average daily traffic (AADT) counts on each road link (line vectors);
- Vehicle speed profiles by road type;
- A land cover surface with classification types that can be linked to surface roughness coefficients (polygon vectors);
- Building footprints with height information (polygon vectors);
- Meteorological station measurements to calculate the average temperature in degrees Celsius, and the wind direction profile for the study period (point vectors).

In brief, the coordinates of each receptor are assigned to the closest building. The building façade that is likely to experience the highest noise levels is identified, and a receptor (point) is placed 1m away from the building. A GIS operation locates all major roads within a 1000m radius and all minor roads within a 100m radius of each receptor. These roads are then divided into a series of source points at 10m intervals along each road segment. Next, rays are projected from each of the noise source points to the receptor location as a direct path, and the land cover types and buildings along this line are ascertained. For each ray path in turn, the noise level at each source point can be calculated using traffic flow data and the empirical relationships defined by CNOSSOS-EU. Following this, the receptor noise level is estimated according to the specific environments along the ray path and the CNOSSOS-EU sound propagation algorithms.

The model constructs five noise metrics that are 'A' frequency weighted. This weighting of the audible frequencies is designed to reflect the response of the human ear to noise (between 500 Hz and 6 kHz):

- **Lday** is the A-weighted equivalent noise level (Leq) over the 12-hour day period (07:00-19:00), also known as the day noise indicator.
- **Levening** is the A-weighted equivalent noise level (Leq) over the 4-hour evening period 19:00-23:00 hours, also known as evening noise indicator.
- **Lnight** is the A-weighted equivalent noise level (Leq) over the 8-hour night period of 23:00 to 07:00 hours, also known as the night noise indicator.
- **LAeq16** is the A-weighted equivalent noise level (Leq) over the 16-hour day period of 07:00 to 23:00 hours.
- **Lden** is the A-weighted equivalent noise level (Leq) over a whole day, but with a penalty of +10 dB(A) for night-time noise (22:00-07:00) and +5 dB(A) for evening noise (19:00-23:00). Also known as the day-evening-night noise indicator.

TABLE 1: Noise exposure metrics

The following diagram, adapted from Gulliver et al (2015), describes the workflow of the CNOSSOS-EU model in PostgreSQL:

FIGURE 1: Workflow of the CNOSSOS-EU road-transport noise model

4. Variability in noise levels around buildings

4.1 Maximum exposure

The current implementation of the CNOSSOS-EU model for road-transport noise exposure models the building façade that is likely to experience the most noise levels is identified using the following protocol:

- Receptor locations (red points) are mapped in relation to the roads (black lines) and building structures (grey polygons).
- Receptor locations are assigned to the nearest building.
- A continuous line is then created, which marks the extent of each receptor building +1m. Then a series of candidate receptor points separated by 1m are created around the building extent.
- Remove any candidate receptor points that fall inside or <1m from an adjacent building.
- Identify the candidate receptor point that is most likely to be located on the loudest façade by calculating the vehicle count of the nearest road, inverse to the roads distance.
- Buildings selected with an associated receiver.

FIGURE 2: Receptor placement

For practicality purposes, the current script only models the point of maximum exposure at any given residential address. Model runtimes of approximately 15 hours are recorded for 10,000 locations, and 125 hours for 30,000 locations (See Figure 3). The CNOSSOS-EU script only uses parallel processing in parts; however, this can be worked around by submitting smaller batches to the HPC system at Leicester.

FIGURE 3: CNOSSOS-EU runtime benchmarked on a session with 8-processing cores and 64GB ram.

The inverse calculation of the maximum point of exposure on a building is also calculated (i.e., the building façade point with the lowest inverse distance weighted AADT count, defined by the attributes of the nearest road). The quiet façade, or QSIDE, is used to explore the variation in noise exposure at dwellings.

4.2 Exposure variability

The road-transport noise model is also capable of modelling the distribution of exposure around buildings, dependant on the number of receptor addresses.

FIGURE 4: Variations in residential exposure

The receptor generation script (Appendix 10.1) returns the loudest (“t3_best_receptors”), quietest (“t3_quite_receptors”) and all valid façade points (“t2_receptors”) around each receptor building. The receptor points table entering the CNOSSOS-EU model can be updated to reflect this (Appendix 10.5-10.7)

5. Noise exposure estimates for road-transport.

5.1 ALSPAC Cohort (2013)

As a proof of concept, residential exposures to road-transport noise pollution in 2013 were modelled for 81,121 locations across the Greater Bristol area (the former county of Avon), which is located in the Southwest of England. These locations cover all addresses of the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC) cohort that have been lived in at some point since 1993.

AADT counts by vehicle class on individual road-links were extracted from the address routed regression model of UK traffic in 2013, created by Morley and Gulliver (2016). The Ordnance Survey (OS) MasterMap topographic layer provided detailed land cover and building height information, which were used to inform how terrain influences the propagation of sound. The OS is Great Britain's national mapping agency with their products deemed to meet the gold standard for local geospatial data in England; it is updated every 6 months and has a horizontal RMSE (root mean squared error) of 0.5m. Annual average temperature and wind profile measurements were obtained from six nearby meteorological stations (within 10km of the Avon administrative boundary).

Figures 5-6 show the range and distribution of exposures at 81,121 postcode locations across the Greater Bristol area in 2013. They also illustrate how the distribution of exposure changes when including the minor road component.

FIGURE 5: Estimated noise levels at 81,121 locations within the Greater Bristol area for the 16-hour daytime period (LAEQ-16) in 2013, from CNOSSOS-EU models that consider (a) only traffic on major roads, and (b) traffic from all road types.

FIGURE 6: Estimated noise levels at 81,121 locations within the Greater Bristol area for the 8-hour night period (L_{night}) in 2013, from CNOSSOS-EU models that consider (a) only traffic on major roads, and (b) traffic from all road types.

These outputs demonstrate that major roads are largely responsible for exposures at and above 60dB, however, a large proportion of the population are to some extent sheltered from such exposures (i.e., by distance and or urban structures). The influence of minor roads is key to higher levels of noise exposure for the majority of the population.

The Environmental Noise Directive (END) currently only requires EU countries to publish noise maps and noise management action plans every 5 years for “major” sources in agglomerations with more than 100,000 inhabitants. For roads, major sources are those that record >3,000,000 vehicle passages per year. The histograms above show that there is a substantial exposure misclassification by only focusing on the noise contributions from major roads, which we are able to rectify with our modelling approach.

The following table summarises the distribution of noise from road-transport on major and minor roads for the 81,121 residential locations, according to the specified noise measurement statistic:

Percentile	Lday (dB)	Leve (dB)	Lnight (dB)	Laeq-16 (dB)	Lden (dB)
0 (Min)	38.0	38.0	38.0	38.0	43.8
10	45.2	42.4	40.1	44.6	46.4
20	48.7	45.4	42.1	48.0	48.6
30	50.7	47.1	43.5	50.0	50.1
40	51.9	48.3	44.5	51.3	51.1
50 (Med)	52.9	49.3	45.2	52.3	51.9
60	53.9	50.3	46.1	53.2	52.8
70	55.1	51.5	47.2	54.4	53.9
80	57.0	53.4	49.1	56.4	55.9
90	61.2	57.7	53.4	60.6	60.1
100 (Max)	104.0	100.5	96.3	103.4	103.0

TABLE 2: The distribution of estimated noise levels at 81,121 locations within the Greater Bristol area, from CNOSSOS-EU models that consider traffic from all road types (major and minor roads).

5.2 Approach for scaling the 2013 noise exposure estimates.

Annual average exposure levels from road-transport noise are typically relatively stable over time, with large changes in the decibel levels requiring several hundred more vehicles entering the nearby roads. Such changes are only likely to occur under new traffic management policies, such as the construction of new roads or the rerouting of traffic. As such, the noise model outputs can simply be scaled in accordance with total AADT count changes over time, rather than rerunning the noise exposure models.

Two scaling processes were conducted on the 2013 model outputs for the ALSPAC cohort, the choice of which was dependant on the year of exposure. Annual average noise exposures were calculated for all address locations between 1993 and 2020.

5.2.1 Local scaling factors (2000 – 2020)

Local scaling factors were applied for years between 2000 and 2020. Here, roadside vehicle counts in the UK were accessed from the Department for Transport (DfT) regional traffic statistics (<https://roadtraffic.dft.gov.uk/regions>). For each site, a series of ratios (scaling factors) were created by comparing AADT counts in a given year, to AADT counts in 2013. Sites were only included in the analysis if they: (a) recorded an AADT count for each of the 21 years, and (b) if each of the recorded AADT counts ≥ 500 . In total, there are 320 valid traffic count sites located within 3km of the Greater Bristol study area.

Potential outliers in the annual AADT ratios were removed by capping the upper and lower values, using a simple and commonly used trimming approach of $1.5 * IQR$. Inverse distance weighting was then used to calculate a scaling factor that is unique to each receptor location for a specified year, based on the proximity of traffic count stations (i.e., a gravity approach that creates a spatially weighted average value for each receptor, prioritising the AADT ratio of nearby stations). The distance-weighted means are

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based on the AADT ratios of all sites within a 3km search radius. If a receptor is >3km from a traffic count site, then the scaling factor is based on the citywide average scaling factor for that year.

5.2.2 Local scaling factors (1993 – 1999)

Citywide scaling factors were applied for all years prior to 2000 due to the lack of local count point data. A single AADT count for the entire City of Bristol each year was obtained from the DfT travel survey data between 1993 and 1999 (<https://roadtraffic.dft.gov.uk/local-authorities/144>). Citywide annual scaling factors (ratio) were created by comparing AADT counts in any given year, to AADT counts in 2000.

These citywide scaling factors were applied to the noise estimates created for 2000 (i.e., the 2013 model outputs are first locally scaled back to 2000 to obtain some historic local variation, with a citywide scaling factor then applied to backdate the exposures further).

5.2.3 How the scaling factors are applied

The decibel (dB) is a nonlinear measurement unit of sound intensity, recorded on a ten times base-10 logarithmic scale. Therefore, the scaling factors must be applied to the anti-logged measurements of noise, with the resulting product transformed back to the decibel scale using the following approach:

Example 1:

Inputs

- Lden 2013 (dB) = 55
- 2018 AADT scaling factor = 1.27 (i.e. traffic was 27% higher in 2018 than 2013)

Calculation

1. Divide the 2013 noise measurement (dB) by 10, and anti-log

$$a = 10^{(55/10)}$$

$$a = 316,228$$
2. Apply the 2018 AADT Scaling Factor

$$b = a * 1.27$$

$$b = 401,609$$
3. Return the scaled inverse-noise value back to the decibel scale

$$c = 10 * \text{LOG}_{10}(b)$$

$$c = 56.04 \text{ dB}$$

This example shows that a 27% increase in traffic will result in a 1.04 dB increase in residential noise exposure levels.

Example 2:

The following approach can be used to create an annual average noise estimate, which accounts for a change of address:

Inputs

- Residential location 1
 - Lden 2013 (dB) = 50
 - 2018 AADT scaling factor = 1.95
 - Days spent at location 1 in 2018 = 200 out of 365
- Residential location 2
 - Lden 2013 (dB) = 65
 - 2018 AADT scaling factor = 1.25
 - Days spent at location 2 in 2018 = 165 out of 365

Calculation

1. For each location, divide the 2013 noise measurement (dB) by 10, and anti-log
 - $a1 = 10^{(50/10)}$
 - $a2 = 10^{(65/10)}$
2. Apply the 2018 AADT Scaling Factor that is unique to each location
 - $b1 = a1 * 1.95$
 - $b2 = a2 * 1.25$
3. Then construct a weighted average of the scaled inverse-noise values, using the amount of time (days) spent at each place of residence
 - $c = (b1 * (200/365)) + (b2 * (165/365))$
4. Return the scaled inverse-noise value back to the decibel scale
 - $d = 10 * \text{LOG}_{10}(c)$
 - $d = 62.77 \text{ dB}$

5.2.4 ALSPAC Cohort scaled estimates (1993-2020)

The ALSPAC cohort contains annual average residential exposures from 1993 to 2020.

Figure 7, displays how road-traffic levels have changed over the 21 years between 2000 and 2020. AADT counts have remained relatively stable (as shown by the box plots) with more local variation occurring further back in time.

A substantial change in traffic is only seen in 2020, which is a result of the COVID-19 lockdowns. Here, traffic fell by around 21% (median); however, this had a minimal influence on noise exposure as shown in figure 8. The median Night value in 2013 is 45.35 dB compared to 44.18 dB in 2020.

FIGURE 7: Box (quartile) and Whisker (95% confidence intervals) plot displaying the distribution of residential AADT scaling factors at 81,121 locations within the Greater Bristol area

FIGURE 8: Box (quartile) and Whisker (95% confidence intervals) plot of residentially scaled Lnight exposures from road-transport at 81,121 locations within the Greater Bristol area

5.2.5 Bristol City center road-transport noise estimates (2013)

Additional road-transport noise modelling work has been conducted in Bristol City centre at postcode centroids (representative of 15 properties) in 2013. The following figures display how noise propagates from major and minor roads, and the sheltering influence of structures in the urban environment.

FIGURE 9: Lday exposures from all road sources in Bristol City Centre (Period 23:00–07:00 hours)

FIGURE 10: Lnight exposures from all road sources in Bristol City Centre (Period 23:00–07:00 hours)

6. Applying the model with open-source or local data

The following spatial layers (shapefile formats with the specified file names) are required to run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for any study area of interest:

Item	Description	Expected File Name	File Format	Data Provider
1	Study area extent (optional)	-	Polygon vector (SHP)	
2	Receptor locations	postcodes	Points vector (SHP)	Local Cohorts
3	Meteorological station wind profiles	met_wind_2013	Points vector (SHP)	University of Leicester
4	Meteorological station temperatures	met_temp_2013	Points vector (SHP)	University of Leicester
5	Continuous land cover surface	mm_landcover	Polygons vector (SHP)	Local government, national mapping agency, or OpenStreetMap (ISGlobal)
6	Buildings with height attributes	mm_buildings	Polygons vector (SHP)	Local government, national mapping agency, or OpenStreetMap (ISGlobal)
7	Road network	routed_aadt	Lines vector (SHP)	Deliverable 3.2 - Traffic flow prediction

TABLE 3: Spatial data requirements for the open-source CNOSSOS-EU road-transport model

6.1 Study area extent

A polygon or bounding box covering the study area. This spatial layer is useful for validating the coverage of your spatial datasets throughout the study area. For example, a polygon that defines the administrative boundary of Bristol, Barcelona, or Amsterdam may be used.

6.2 Receptor locations

A series of X-Y receptor point locations projected in an appropriate planar coordinate system (i.e., units measured in meters). The model requires each row of the shapefile to have a unique:

- (1) Alphanumeric value in a field named **“postcode”**
- (2) Geometry field called **“geom”**

Georeferenced receptor addresses need to be provided by the individual cohorts that are part of the Equal-Life project. To preserve anonymity requirements, certain cohorts may also need to generate additional random address locations.

6.3 Meteorological station wind profiles

A series of X-Y weather station points projected in an appropriate planar coordinate system, which profiles the annual wind direction at each location.

The wind profile records the proportion (fraction) of valid hourly wind measurements in a year that are from the northeast (0-89°), southeast (90-179°), southwest (180-269°), and southwest (270-359°). The four wind fraction fields are required to exactly sum to one at each location.

The model requires each row of the shapefile to have a unique:

- (1) Numeric value of each weather station in a field named *"src_id"*
- (2) Character string stating the name of each weather station in a field named *"src_name"*
- (3) Four numeric wind fraction fields named: *"ne"*, *"se"*, *"sw"*, and *"nw"*
- (4) Geometry field called *"geom"*

Meteorological datasets may be directly sourced from local providers. Alternatively, records can be accessed from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Integrated Surface Database (ISD) (www.ncdc.noaa.gov/isd). The ISD contains global hourly and synoptic observations compiled from more than 30,000 surface meteorological sites around the world, which are compiled into a common ASCII format.

The University of Leicester has capacity to extract and create the required meteorological information from NOAA, if a bounding box of the study area (extent) can be provided. It is recommended that the hourly observations are weighted by month-of-year, and measurement sites should meet the 75% data capture threshold.

6.4 Meteorological station temperatures

A series of X-Y weather station points projected in an appropriate planar coordinate system, which provide the annual average hourly-recorded temperature (°C). See section 2.1.3 for information.

The model requires each row of the shapefile to have a unique:

- (1) Numeric value of each weather station in a field named *"src_id"*
- (2) Character string stating the name of each weather station in a field named *"src_name"*
- (3) Numeric value recording the average dry air temperature named *"air_temp"*
- (4) Geometry field called *"geom"*

See section 7.3 for further details, and information on how the dataset can be obtained.

6.5 Continuous land cover surface

A polygon topography layer that describes all forms of land cover in the study area. This also contains buildings with height attributes.

The model requires each row of the shapefile to have a unique:

- (1) Numeric value for each land parcel named *"mm_id"*

- (2) Character string stating the land cover type named *“legend”*
- (3) Numeric value recording the object height in meters names *“hgt”*.
- (4) Geometry field called *“geom”*

Please note that object heights have only been collected for structures and buildings for model runs in the UK.

In version 1.4 of our CNOSSOS functions, buildings and structures equal or greater to 4.5m in height are provided a surface roughness coefficient g-value of 0 (hard surfaces), and all other land features are provided with a g-value of 1 (soft surfaces). **This “soft surface” approach of building vs all other landforms can be applied if land cover classifications are insufficient or unavailable.** This approach is to be used if OpenStreetMap data with an incomplete set of land cover records is used.

If detailed land cover type descriptions are available from local datasets, then the script in Appendix 10.3 can be read by PostgreSQL to overwrite the default functions found in Appendix 10.2 that are used by the approach above (i.e., use a “mixed surface” approach). Please note that the ground cover function in Appendix 10.3 will need to be updated to correspond to the descriptive land cover types in your data. The following table should be used to help assign land cover types to g-coefficient values:

Description	Type	ISO 9613-2	NMPB 2008
Parameter		G	G
Very soft (snow or moss-like)	A	1	1
Soft forest floor (short, dense heather-like or thick moss)	B	1	1
Uncompacted, loose ground (turf, grass, loose soil)	C	1	1
Normal uncompacted ground (forest floors, pasture field)	D	1	1
Compacted field and gravel (compacted lawns, park area)	E	0	0.7
Compacted dense ground (gravel road, parking lot, ISO 10844)	F	0	0.3
Hard surfaces (mostly normal asphalt, concrete)	G	0	0
Very hard and dense surfaces (dense asphalt, concrete, water)	H	0	0

TABLE 4: Correspondence of land cover types to ground surface roughness properties across ISO 9613-2 and NMPB 2008 (Kephelopoulos et al 2014, p.413)

The land classification system found in the OS MasterMap product, limits us to the use of binary surface roughness coefficients for the UK (i.e. in accordance with ISO 9613-2).

The impact of running the “soft-surface” (i.e., building vs all other landforms) and “mixed-surface” assumptions for different land cover types has been investigated across a sample of 6,259 postcodes in the UK county of Devon:

- The “soft surface” model on average underestimates exposure by 0.5dB (SD)
- Less than 4% of the receptors had a difference of more than 2dB
- These differences were consistent across the five noise metrics of Lday, Levening, Lnight, LAeq16, and Lden.

6.6 Buildings with height attributes

A polygon layer that only contains the buildings with height attributes, typically extracted from the aforementioned topography layer.

The model requires each row of the shapefile to have a unique:

- (1) Numeric value for each building entry named ***“gid”***
- (2) Alphanumeric value for each building entry named ***“os_topo_to”***
- (3) Numeric value recording the object height in meters names ***“relhmax”***
- (4) Geometry field called ***“geom”***

6.7 Road network

A collection of line features projected in an appropriate planar coordinate system, which is representative of the road-network. The model requires each row of the shapefile to contain the following information:

- (1) A character field named ***“road type”*** that describes each road link in accordance with the 10-fold OpenStreetMap classification scheme:

OSM ROAD TYPE	MINOR ROAD = 1
residential	1
unclassified	1
tertiary	1
secondary	1
primary	0
primary link	0
trunk	0
trunk link	0
motorway	0
motorway link	0

TABLE 5: OpenStreetMap road classification scheme

- (2) A binary field called ***“minor”*** needs adding to identify the minor roads in the OpenStreetMap road classification scheme (where minor = 1 and major = 0).
- (3) Annual Average Daily Traffic (AADT) counts by vehicle type, stored in six fields named ***“c1”***, ***“c2”***, ***“c3”***, ***“c4a”***, ***“c4b”***, and ***“allmv”***. Vehicles are classified in accordance with the following scheme:

Category	Name	Description	Vehicle category in EC Whole Vehicle Type Approval ⁽¹⁾
1	Light motor vehicles	Passenger cars, delivery vans ≤ 3.5 tons, SUVs ⁽²⁾ , MPVs ⁽³⁾ including trailers and caravans	M1 and N1
2	Medium heavy vehicles	Medium heavy vehicles, delivery vans > 3.5 tons, buses, touring cars, etc. with two axles and twin tyre mounting on rear axle	M2, M3 and N2, N3
3	Heavy vehicles	Heavy duty vehicles, touring cars, buses, with three or more axles	M2 and N2 with trailer, M3 and N3
4	Powered two-wheelers	4a mopeds, tricycles or quads ≤ 50 cc	L1, L2, L6
		4b motorcycles, tricycles or quads > 50 cc	L3, L4, L5, L7
5	Open category	To be defined according to future needs	N/A

⁽¹⁾ Directive 2007/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 September 2007 (OJ L 263/1 9/10/2007) establishing a framework for the approval of motor vehicles and their trailers, and of systems, components and separate technical units intended for such vehicles

⁽²⁾ Sport Utility Vehicles

⁽³⁾ Multi-Purpose Vehicles

TABLE 6: CNOSSOS-EU vehicle classifications (Kephalopoulos et al 2012, p.31)

- (4) Twenty-four numeric fields named “*p0*” to “*p23*”, which represent the hourly percentage of heavy vehicles across the day. The default [TRANEX](#) profile is currently used by all roads in the UK model:

Hour	P0	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7
% Heavy vehicles	0.78	0.53	0.43	0.45	0.67	1.43	3.32	5.92
Hour	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
% Heavy vehicles	6.53	5.87	6.05	6.38	6.5	6.56	6.69	7.07
Hour	P16	P17	P18	P19	P20	P21	P22	P23
% Heavy vehicles	7.77	7.8	6.23	4.45	3.17	2.37	1.79	1.21

TABLE 7: Hourly percentage of heavy vehicles on UK roads (Morley et al 2015)

The UK heavy vehicle profile for 2013 may be applied to other countries if local data is not available.

- (5) Five numeric fields recording the daily average road speeds in km/hour on each road class, by vehicle type. These fields are named “*speed1*”, “*speed2*”, “*speed3*”, “*speed4a*”, and “*speed4b*”. The speeds correspond to the vehicle type number system used by the AADT counts (i.e., “*speed2*” is linked to vehicle count “*c2*”).

OSM ROAD TYPE	SPEED1	SPEED2	SPEED3	SPEED4A	SPEED4B
residential	32	32	32	32	32
unclassified	32	32	32	32	32
secondary	48	48	48	48	48
tertiary	48	48	48	48	48
primary	96	80	64	50	96
primary link	96	80	64	50	96
trunk	96	96	80	50	96
trunk link	96	96	80	50	96
motorway	112	112	96	50	112
motorway link	112	112	96	50	112

TABLE 8: UK daily average road speeds in km/hour on each road class, by vehicle type

Vehicle speeds may need to be updated in accordance with national speed limits in different countries.

Deliverable 3.2 will generate a local road network dataset with components 1-3 (road type, is minor, and AADT counts by vehicle class).

6.8 Accessing data from OpenStreetMap (OSM)

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a free, open geographic database updated and maintained by a community of volunteers who collect data from surveys, trace from aerial imagery, and import information from other freely licensed geodata sources.

Information on land use, building footprints and building heights may be completely or partially available for the study areas of interest. However, it is recommended that the appropriate local government agency is first contacted to see if more comprehensive versions of the datasets, with a higher degree of accuracy, exist.

The availability of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data can be checked in the R Programming language (<https://www.r-project.org>), using the following code:

```
#### Title: Examine and extract the available features in Barcelona from OpenStreetMap (OSM)

## Check required packages are installed, otherwise install from CRAN
req_packages <- c("sf", "osmdata", "ggplot2")
new_packages <- req_packages[!(req_packages %in% installed.packages()[,"Package"])]
if(length(new_packages) > 0) {install.packages(new_packages, repos = "http://cran.us.r-project.org")}

## Load required packages
library(sf)
library(osmdata)
library(ggplot2)

## See the list of the available features from OpenStreetMap (OSM)
osmdata::available_features()

# Creating bounding box for Barcelona
barcelona_bb <- osmdata::getbb("Barcelona")
barcelona_bb

## (1) Extract street data in Barcelona

## See the available "highway" data (URL: https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway)
osmdata::available_tags("highway")

## Retrieving data of streets in Barcelona
barcelona_streets <- barcelona_bb %>%
  opq() %>%
  add_osm_feature("highway", c('residential','unclassified','secondary','tertiary',
                              'primary','primary_link','trunk','trunk_link','motorway','motorway_link')) %>%
  osmdata_sf()
names(barcelona_streets)

## Cleaning the street extract
barcelona_streets <- barcelona_streets$osm_lines
str(barcelona_streets)
plot(barcelona_streets["highway"])

## (2) Extract landuse in Barcelona

osmdata::available_tags("landuse")
```



```

barcelona_land <- barcelona_bb %>%
  opq() %>%
  add_osm_feature("landuse") %>%
  osmdata_sf()
names(barcelona_land)

barcelona_land <- rbind(barcelona_land$osm_polygons[,c("landuse", "geometry")],
  barcelona_land$osm_multipolygons[,c("landuse", "geometry")])
str(barcelona_land)
unique(barcelona_land$landuse)
plot(barcelona_land["landuse"])

## (3) Extract buildings in Barcelona

osmdata::available_tags("building")

barcelona_build <- barcelona_bb %>%
  opq() %>%
  add_osm_feature("building") %>%
  osmdata_sf()
names(barcelona_build)

barcelona_build_2 <- rbind(barcelona_build$osm_polygons[,c("building", "height", "geometry")])
str(barcelona_build_2)
plot(barcelona_build)

```


7. Application of the noise model to other cohorts in Equal-Life

Using the traffic model developed in WP3, Task 3.3 (see D3.2), the CNOSSOS-EU noise model (see Appendices for code) was applied to BREATHE (Spain), WALNUTS (Spain) and STARS (Sweden) with outputs shown here, and are also applied in The Netherlands (ABCD, PIAMA – data available in Q1 of 2024). These were all areas where the project team did not have access to any traffic flow data. In all cases, every public road has been modelled and included in the noise predictions, unlike e.g., END mapping which usually only includes major roads.

We used OSM for the road network and building footprints (see section 6.8), CORINE (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover>) for land cover, and building heights from two sources: 1) UrbanAtlas (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/urban-atlas/building-height-2012>) for the major cities (10m grid), and 2) Global Human Settlement (https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ghs_buH2023.php) data for other locations (30m grid). The gridded building height data was converted to points and intersected with OSM building geometry. The median building height was taken for buildings containing multiple points. Buildings without allocated heights from this step were imputed using inverse distance weighting.

In each case we applied the noise model to predict the loudest façade and quietest façade (i.e., in-line with the QSIDE principle). We mapped the predicted noise levels for visual inspection. We are unable to show those maps in this report due to the confidentiality agreement bound by the project. We show the distributions of predicted noise levels, as follows.

For each address location we produced LDAY, LEVE, LNIGHT, LDEN, and LAEQ16,hr for the loudest and quietest facades, and separately for ‘major roads’ and ‘all roads’ (i.e. including major and minor roads).

Figure 10 shows LAEQ16,hr for the BREATHE cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade. Figure 11 shows LNIGHT for BREATHE: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade. Figures 12 and 13 show the same metrics for the WALNUTS cohort and Figures 14 and 15 shows the same metrics for the STARS cohort. In all three cohorts there are substantially different distributions when including minor roads in the noise calculation.

The difference between the loudest and quietest façades could be used as a measure of uncertainty in the main exposure (loudest façade), or the quietest façade noise level used as an alternative exposure. Using data for ‘all roads’, in the STARS cohort, for example, the median difference for LDAY was 7.5 dB(A) and for LNIGHT was 4.31 dB(A). The 90th % difference was 16.2 dB(A) for LDAY and 11.2 dB(A) for LNIGHT. This array of data (major/minor roads; loudest/quietest façade) will allow new analysis across geographically diverse cohorts.

New noise modelling data is available for ALSPAC, BREATHE, STARS, and WALNUTS, with ABCD and PIAMA to follow by March 2024, and the remaining cohorts by summer 2024. We are in the process of undertaking the enrichment of this data with cohorts.

Figure 10. Modelled LAEQ16,hr for the BREATHE cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

Figure 11. Modelled L_{NIGHT} for the BREATHE cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

Figure 12. Modelled LAEQ_{16,hr} for the WALNUTS cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

Figure 13. Modelled LNIght for the WALNUTS cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

Figure 14. Modelled LAEQ16,hr for the STARS cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

Figure 15. Modelled LNIGHT for the STARS cohort: A) loudest façade, and B) quietest façade.

8. Embedding new sound-based metrics and models for the exposome

As part of future work, in conjunction with the publication of D3.2 and D3.5, we aim to enhance the CNOSSOS implementation with new models and metrics.

We aim to convert estimated traffic counts for each road link to calculate the intermittency (s) of each vehicle with respect to vehicle speeds (m/s). Currently, average speeds per OSM road category are applied in our implementation of CNOSSOS. We will introduce a random deviation to vehicle speeds, superimposed on the cumulative distribution of vehicle speed by OSM category described in D3.5, section 3.4. Hence, we are able to treat *Lclose* (nearest local road) and *Lfar* (long-distance propagation) separately for vehicles speeds and estimates of sound power (L_w).

For *Lclose*, we will estimate L_w for individual vehicles, following the procedure described in Section 3.2 of deliverable 3.5. An estimate of sound using standard procedures for *Lfar* will be separate. It follows that we will be able to estimate intermittency ratio, LA50, L10-L90 etc. (see Section 3.5, D3.5), new sleep disturbance metrics, and $L_{A,50}$ – as an indicator of disturbance in restorative places - for *Lclose*, as well as LAeq metrics for all roads. Using the procedure described in Section 4 of this report we will estimate noise levels for the loudest and quietest façade, including new metrics where applicable.

Attenuation of outdoor sound levels indoors at dwellings can be made using an empirical model developed in D3.5. We will expand the data available for estimating indoor indicators by using a dataset that is available for 49 dwellings in London, where contemporaneous outdoor and indoor measurements were made over 72 hours.

9. Importing the datasets into PostgreSQL

Install PostgreSQL version 11.18 from <https://www.postgresql.org/download/>

Please ensure that the PostGIS extension is selected when installing.

Open the pgAdmin 4 software on your local machine.

Create a database called "noise_test" and import the PostGIS spatial database functions, using the following guide: https://postgis.net/workshops/postgis-intro/creating_db.html

To import your spatial layers into the PostgreSQL database, open the PostGIS Shapefile and DBF Loader Exporter software on your local machine. Please refer to the following guidance for importing shapefiles: https://postgis.net/workshops/postgis-intro/loading_data.html

The CNOSSOS-EU model can then be run using the scripts found in Appendix 10.1, 10.2, 10.3 (optional), and 10.4.

10. References

European Council (2002). Directive 2002/49/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 June 2002 relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0049>

Gulliver J, Morley DW, Vienneau D, Fabbri F, Bell M, Goodman P, Beevers S, Dajnak D, Kelly FJ, and Fecht D. (2015). Development of an open-source road traffic noise model for exposure assessment. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, Volume 74, pp.183-193

Kephalopoulos S, Paviotti M, and Anfosso-Lédée F. (2012). Common Noise Assessment Methods in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU). EUR 25379 EN. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, JRC72550. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2788/31776>

Morley DW, de Hoogh K, Fecht D, Fabbri F, Bell M, Goodman PS, Elliott P, Hodgson S, Hansell AL, and Gulliver J. (2015). International scale implementation of the CNOSSOS-EU road traffic noise prediction model for epidemiological studies. *Environmental Pollution*, Volume 206, pp.332-341

Morley DW, and Gulliver J. (2016). Methods to improve traffic flow and noise exposure estimation on minor roads. *Environ Pollution*, Volume 216, pp.746-754

11. Appendices

11.1 PostgreSQL: CNOSSOS-EU maximum exposure receptor generation

```

-- #####
-- ## Title: CNOSSOS-EU Maximum Exposure Receptor Generation Script (Version 1.7)
-- ## Authors: Calvin Jephcote (University of Leicester)
-- ## Date: 09/07/2020
-- #####

-- #####
-- ## Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License"). You may not use this file except in compliance with the License.
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-- ## Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS"
-- ## BASIS, WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
-- ## See the License for the specific language governing permissions and limitations under the License.
-- ##
-- ## Preliminary Steps:
-- ## Create a spatial database, see: https://postgis.net/workshops/postgis-intro/creating\_db.html
-- ## Import the following shapefiles using PostGIS, see: https://postgis.net/workshops/postgis-intro/loading\_data.html
-- ##
-- ## Required shapefiles:
-- ## "mm_buildings" >>>>>>>> OS MasterMap building polygons
-- ## "postcodes" >>>>>>>> Postcode points
-- ## "routed_aadt" >>>>>>>> UK road network
-- #####

-- ##### Step 0: Prepare the road network layer for the placement of receptors, and for the CNOSSOS-EU noise calculations

-- ##### Step 0A: Clip the roads network layer to only include those roads within 2km of the receptor postcodes.
-- ##### This will increase the speed of any code that uses a geographical lookup (i.e. nearest neighbour joins).

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s0_clipped_roads;
DROP INDEX IF EXISTS idx0;
CREATE TABLE s0_clipped_roads as
(SELECT roads.*
FROM(
    SELECT ST_Union(ST_Buffer(geom, 2000)) AS geom
    FROM postcodes) as extent
CROSS JOIN LATERAL(
    SELECT *
    FROM routed_aadt
    WHERE ST_Intersects(geom, extent.geom)
) roads);
CREATE INDEX idx0 ON s0_clipped_roads USING gist(geom);

-- ##### Step 0B: Check for, and if required fix any geographic errors in the road network (i.e. self-intersections).
-- ##### If the geographic attributes of any table values cannot be fixed, then remove (i.e. any rows with no defined geometries)

UPDATE s0_clipped_roads SET geom=ST_MAKEVALID(geom) WHERE NOT ST_ISVALID(geom);
DELETE FROM s0_clipped_roads WHERE NOT st_isvalid(s0_clipped_roads.geom);

-- ##### Step 0C: Create a table containing speed and flow characteristics by road-type ("road_classification").
-- ##### Then join this table to the clipped road network ("s0_clipped_roads")

drop table if exists road_classification;
create table road_classification
(
    ROADTYPE character varying(15),
    P0 double precision,
    P1 double precision,
    P2 double precision,

```



```

P3 double precision,
P4 double precision,
P5 double precision,
P6 double precision,
P7 double precision,
P8 double precision,
P9 double precision,
P10 double precision,
P11 double precision,
P12 double precision,
P13 double precision,
P14 double precision,
P15 double precision,
P16 double precision,
P17 double precision,
P18 double precision,
P19 double precision,
P20 double precision,
P21 double precision,
P22 double precision,
P23 double precision,
SPEED1 integer,
SPEED2 integer,
SPEED3 integer,
SPEED4A integer,
SPEED4B integer
);
insert into road_classification values ('residential', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 32, 32, 32, 32, 32);
insert into road_classification values ('unclassified', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 32, 32, 32, 32, 32);
insert into road_classification values ('secondary', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 48, 48, 48, 48, 48);
insert into road_classification values ('tertiary', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 48, 48, 48, 48, 48);
insert into road_classification values ('primary', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 96, 80, 64, 50, 96);
insert into road_classification values ('primary_link', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69,
7.07, 7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 96, 80, 64, 50, 96);
insert into road_classification values ('trunk', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07, 7.77,
7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 96, 96, 80, 50, 96);
insert into road_classification values ('trunk_link', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 96, 96, 80, 50, 96);
insert into road_classification values ('motorway', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69, 7.07,
7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 112, 112, 96, 50, 112);
insert into road_classification values ('motorway_link', 0.78, 0.53, 0.43, 0.45, 0.67, 1.43, 3.32, 5.92, 6.53, 5.87, 6.05, 6.38, 6.5, 6.56, 6.69,
7.07, 7.77, 7.8, 6.23, 4.45, 3.17, 2.37, 1.79, 1.21, 112, 112, 96, 50, 112);

-- ## Join "s0_clipped_roads" and "road_classification"
ALTER TABLE s0_clipped_roads
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P0 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P1 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P2 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P3 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P4 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P5 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P6 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P7 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P8 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P9 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P10 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P11 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P12 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P13 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P14 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P15 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P16 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P17 double precision,

```



```

ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P18 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P19 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P20 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P21 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P22 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS P23 double precision,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS SPEED1 integer,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS SPEED2 integer,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS SPEED3 integer,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS SPEED4A integer,
ADD COLUMN IF NOT EXISTS SPEED4B integer;

UPDATE s0_clipped_roads
SET P0 = road_classification.P0,
    P1 = road_classification.P1,
    P2 = road_classification.P2,
    P3 = road_classification.P3,
    P4 = road_classification.P4,
    P5 = road_classification.P5,
    P6 = road_classification.P6,
    P7 = road_classification.P7,
    P8 = road_classification.P8,
    P9 = road_classification.P9,
    P10 = road_classification.P10,
    P11 = road_classification.P11,
    P12 = road_classification.P12,
    P13 = road_classification.P13,
    P14 = road_classification.P14,
    P15 = road_classification.P15,
    P16 = road_classification.P16,
    P17 = road_classification.P17,
    P18 = road_classification.P18,
    P19 = road_classification.P19,
    P20 = road_classification.P20,
    P21 = road_classification.P21,
    P22 = road_classification.P22,
    P23 = road_classification.P23,
    SPEED1 = road_classification.SPEED1,
    SPEED2 = road_classification.SPEED2,
    SPEED3 = road_classification.SPEED3,
    SPEED4A = road_classification.SPEED4A,
    SPEED4B = road_classification.SPEED4B
FROM road_classification
WHERE s0_clipped_roads.type = road_classification.roadtype;

ALTER TABLE s0_clipped_roads RENAME COLUMN type TO road type;

-- #####

-- #### Step 1: Join postcodes to corresponding building, and only keep the buildings with a join
-- #### Join postcode to nearest building NOT using 'st_within' or 'st_contains' as they can be outside building boundary)

drop table if exists s1_receptor_buildings;
drop index if exists idx1a;

CREATE TABLE s1_receptor_buildings AS
(SELECT a.gid, a.postcode, c.toid, c.relhmax, c.geom
FROM postcodes As a
JOIN LATERAL (
SELECT toid, relhmax, geom
FROM mm_buildings AS b
ORDER BY a.geom <-> b.geom
LIMIT 1
) AS c ON true);
create index idx1a on s1_receptor_buildings using gist(geom);

```



```

-- #### Step 1B: Identify buildings that are nearly, if not completely, boxed in by outbuildings (enclosed polygons).
-- #### These receptor buildings and their adjacent structures are then merged to form a single geometry.
-- #### This mitigates the chance of creating invalid candidate receptor points.

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS temp_bigpolygon;
DROP INDEX IF EXISTS temp_idx;
CREATE TABLE temp_bigpolygon as
SELECT      toid, ST_ExteriorRing((ST_DUMP(geom)).geom) as geom
FROM        mm_buildings;
CREATE INDEX temp_idx on temp_bigpolygon USING gist(geom);

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s1_receptor_buildings_rev;
CREATE TABLE s1_receptor_buildings_rev AS
SELECT d.gid, d.postcode, d.toid, d.relhmax, ST_Union(d.geom) as geom
FROM(
    SELECT    d.geom,
             buildings_to_fix.gid, buildings_to_fix.postcode,
             buildings_to_fix.toid, buildings_to_fix.relhmax
    FROM      mm_buildings as d

    INNER JOIN

-- ## Part 1: Identify receptor buildings that have 75% or more of their facades enclosed by other polygons,
-- ## or if a receptor building has less than 10m of their facade not joined to another building

    (SELECT c.*
     FROM   s1_receptor_buildings as c
     INNER JOIN
           (SELECT a.toid
            FROM(
                SELECT toid, ST_ExteriorRing((ST_DUMP(geom)).geom) as geom
                FROM s1_receptor_buildings) as a

                INNER JOIN(
                    SELECT toid, geom
                    FROM temp_bigpolygon) as b

                ON (ST_Intersects(a.geom, b.geom) AND a.toid != b.toid)
                GROUP BY a.toid, a.geom

                HAVING
                    -- ## Select if up to 75% of a buildings facades are adjoined to outbuildings
                    (abs(ST_Length(a.geom) * 0.75) <= abs(sum(ST_Length(ST_Intersection(a.geom, b.geom))))))
                OR
                    -- ## Select if less than 10m of a buildings facade is exposed
                    (10 > abs(ST_Length(a.geom) - sum(ST_Length(ST_Intersection(a.geom, b.geom))))))
                OR
                    -- ## Select if up to 30m of a buildings facades are adjoined to outbuildings
                    (30 < abs(sum(ST_Length(ST_Intersection(a.geom, b.geom))))))

            ) as identify_buildings ON c.toid = identify_buildings.toid) as buildings_to_fix

    -- ## Part 2: Join the receptor buildings of interest, to other nearby building structures within 1m
    -- ## (i.e. the adjacent outbuildings)

    ON ST_DWithin(d.geom, buildings_to_fix.geom, 1)) as d group by gid, postcode, toid, relhmax;

-- ## Part 3: Append the receptor buildings to "s1_receptor_buildings_rev", which did not require their extents adjusting
-- ## to accommodate for outbuildings

INSERT INTO s1_receptor_buildings_rev
SELECT a.*
FROM   s1_receptor_buildings AS a
LEFT JOIN
      s1_receptor_buildings_rev AS b
ON     b.gid = a.gid
WHERE  b.gid IS NULL
ON CONFLICT DO NOTHING;

```



```

DROP INDEX IF EXISTS idx1b;
CREATE INDEX idx1b on s1_receptor_buildings_rev using gist(geom);
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS temp_bigpolygon;

-- #####

-- #### Step 2: Create continuous lines, marking the extent of each building + 1m

drop table if exists s2_building_lines;
drop index if exists idx2;

CREATE TABLE s2_building_lines AS
SELECT *
FROM(
  -- # Part 5: Merge the line segments of each building, to form a continuous line extent for each building.
  -- # Note, "ST_Collect" appears to be at least 10x faster than "ST_Union"
  SELECT toid, postcode, ST_LineMerge(ST_Collect(geom)) as geom

FROM(
  -- # Part 4: Connect the created series of point pairs to form a line geometry
  SELECT toid, postcode, (st_makeline(sp,ep)) as geom

FROM(
  -- # Part 3: Generate a series of start and end points from the linestrings, which define the extent of each building
  -- # These are the start and end points of each facade (i.e. front, back, and side exterior walls)
  SELECT toid, postcode,
  st_pointn(geom, generate_series(1, st_npoints(geom)-1)) as sp,
  st_pointn(geom, generate_series(2, st_npoints(geom) )) as ep

FROM(
  -- # Part 2: Extract the individual linestrings, which define the facades of the building polygon features
  SELECT toid, postcode, (st_dump(st_boundary(geom))).geom as geom

FROM(
  -- # Part 1: Remove holes from polygons
  SELECT toid, postcode, ST_MakePolygon(ST_ExteriorRing(geom)) as geom

FROM(
  -- # Part 0: Extend receptor buildings by 1m in size

  SELECT toid, postcode, ST_Buffer(geom, 1, 'side=left join=bevel') as geom
  FROM s1_receptor_buildings_rev)

as buffered) as filledpoly) as linestrings) as linepoints) as linesegments GROUP BY toid, postcode) buildings;

ALTER TABLE s2_building_lines ADD COLUMN id SERIAL PRIMARY KEY;
create index idx2 on s2_building_lines using gist(geom);

-- #### Step 3A: Create a Function to get the step ratio per line to divide into x.meter steps

create or replace function get_steprat(lgth double precision, x integer)
returns integer as $$
declare step integer;
begin
  if lgth < x then step := 100000;
  else step := cast(trunc(100000 / (lgth / x)) as integer);
  end if;
  return step;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ##### Step 3B: Create 1m spaced points along the extent line of each building

drop table if exists s3_all_points;
drop index if exists idx3;
create table s3_all_points as
with wall as (
    select bl.id, bl.toid, bl.postcode, get_steprat(st_length(bl.geom), 1) as step, bl.geom
    from s2_building_lines as bl
)
select s.id, s.toid, s.postcode, st_lineinterpolatepoint(s.geom, cast(s.pstep as double precision) / 100000) as geom
from (
    select w.id, w.toid, w.postcode, generate_series(w.step / 2, 100000, w.step) as pstep, w.geom
    from wall as w
) as s;

select UpdateGeometrySRID('public', 's3_all_points', 'geom', 27700);
create index idx3 on s3_all_points using gist(geom);

-- #####

-- ##### Step 4A (Revised Approach): Run a Bulk Nearest Neighbour search using Lateral Joins
-- ##### (Points within and less than <1m from any building are removed)

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s4_valid_points;
CREATE TABLE s4_valid_points AS
SELECT
    s3_all_points.*
FROM
    s3_all_points
CROSS JOIN LATERAL
(SELECT toid, geom
 FROM mm_buildings
 ORDER BY s3_all_points.geom <-> mm_buildings.geom
 LIMIT 1) AS buildings
WHERE ST_Distance(buildings.geom, s3_all_points.geom) >= 0.99;

-- ##### Step 4B: Check to see if there are any buildings without a valid receptor point (i.e. all sample points are within another building)
-- ##### If no valid points exist, append all points for the building in question to "s4_valid_points"

INSERT INTO s4_valid_points
SELECT a.*
FROM s3_all_points AS a
LEFT JOIN
    s4_valid_points AS b
ON b.id = a.id
WHERE b.id IS NULL
ON CONFLICT DO NOTHING;

drop index if exists idx4;
create index idx4 on s4_valid_points using gist (geom);

-- ##### Step 5: Run a Bulk Nearest Neighbour search using Lateral Joins
-- ##### For each point, add the distance to the nearest road and its identification fields.
-- ##### For each postcode, return a single receptor point determined by vehicle count and road proximity

-- ##### Step 5A: For each row in the "s4_valid_points" table, return the attributes of the nearest road

drop table if exists s5a_receptors;
drop index if exists idx5a;
CREATE TABLE s5a_receptors AS
SELECT *
FROM(
    SELECT
        s4_valid_points.*,
        roads.gid as roadgid, roads.roadtype, roads.allmv,

```



```

        ST_Distance(roads.geom, s4_valid_points.geom) AS distance
    FROM
        s4_valid_points
    CROSS JOIN LATERAL
        (SELECT gid, roadtype, allmv, geom
         FROM s0_clipped_roads
         ORDER BY s4_valid_points.geom <-> s0_clipped_roads.geom
         LIMIT 1) AS roads
) as nearestneigh;
ALTER TABLE s5a_receptors ADD unique_id serial;
CREATE INDEX idx5a ON s5a_receptors USING gist(geom);

-- #### Step 5B (Revised Approach): Identify postcodes where the best receptor point should be selected purely on distance

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s5b_selection_method;
CREATE TABLE s5b_selection_method AS
SELECT id, postcode, count(id) AS n, min(distance) AS min_dist, max(distance) AS max_dist
FROM s5a_receptors
GROUP BY id, postcode
ORDER BY id ASC;

ALTER TABLE s5b_selection_method ADD near_method integer;
UPDATE s5b_selection_method
SET near_method = CASE
    WHEN n = 1 THEN 1 -- identify postcodes with a single candidate receptor point (n=1)
    WHEN min_dist > 1000 THEN 1 -- identify postcodes where all points are > 1000m from a road link
    ELSE 0
END;

-- #### Step 5C (Revised Approach): Retrieve the best receptor point for a given building

-- ## Calculate the vehicle count of the nearest road, inverse to the distance of the receptor point
ALTER TABLE s5a_receptors DROP COLUMN IF EXISTS inv_allmv;
ALTER TABLE s5a_receptors ADD COLUMN inv_allmv double precision;
UPDATE s5a_receptors SET inv_allmv = allmv / distance;

-- ## Method 1: Selection based on proximity (if all roads are nearby, or the selection or receptor points is limited)
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s5c_best_receptor;
CREATE TABLE s5c_best_receptor AS
SELECT id, unique_id, toid, postcode, roadtype AS near_road, allmv AS road_mv, distance AS road_dist, geom
FROM(
    SELECT a.*,
           rank() OVER (PARTITION BY a.id ORDER BY a.distance ASC, allmv DESC) AS ranked
    FROM s5a_receptors AS a
    LEFT JOIN s5b_selection_method AS b
    ON a.id = b.id
    WHERE b.near_method = 1
    ORDER BY a.id ASC, a.distance ASC) AS c
WHERE ranked = 1;

-- ## Method 2: Selection based on traffic count and proximity (if all roads are further away)
INSERT INTO s5c_best_receptor
SELECT id, unique_id, toid, postcode, roadtype AS near_road, allmv AS road_mv, distance AS road_dist, geom
FROM(
    SELECT a.*,
           rank() OVER (PARTITION BY a.id ORDER BY inv_allmv DESC) AS ranked
    FROM s5a_receptors AS a
    LEFT JOIN s5b_selection_method AS b
    ON a.id = b.id
    WHERE b.near_method = 0 AND a.distance <= 1000
    ORDER BY a.id ASC, inv_allmv DESC, a.allmv DESC, a.distance ASC) AS c
WHERE ranked = 1;

```



```

-- ##### Step 5D: Retrieve the quietest point for a given building (QSIDE)

-- ## Method 1: Selection based on proximity (if all roads are nearby, or the selection or receptor points is limited)
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s5d_quite_receptor;
CREATE TABLE s5d_quite_receptor AS
SELECT id, unique_id, toid, postcode, roadtype AS near_road, allmv AS road_mv, distance AS road_dist, geom
FROM(
    SELECT a.*,
           rank() OVER (PARTITION BY a.id ORDER BY a.distance DESC, allmv ASC) AS ranked
    FROM s5a_receptors AS a
    LEFT JOIN s5b_selection_method AS b
    ON a.id = b.id
    WHERE b.near_method = 1
    ORDER BY a.id ASC, a.distance ASC) AS c
WHERE ranked = 1;

-- ## Method 2: Selection based on traffic count and proximity (if all roads are further away)
INSERT INTO s5d_quite_receptor
SELECT id, unique_id, toid, postcode, roadtype AS near_road, allmv AS road_mv, distance AS road_dist, geom
FROM(
    SELECT a.*,
           rank() OVER (PARTITION BY a.id ORDER BY inv_allmv ASC) AS ranked
    FROM s5a_receptors AS a
    LEFT JOIN s5b_selection_method AS b
    ON a.id = b.id
    WHERE b.near_method = 0 AND a.distance <= 1000
    ORDER BY a.id ASC, inv_allmv DESC, a.allmv DESC, a.distance ASC) AS c
WHERE ranked = 1;

-- ##### Create the final set of output tables

-- Rename output tables
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t1_receptor_buildings;
ALTER TABLE s1_receptor_buildings_rev RENAME TO t1_receptor_buildings;

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t2_receptors;
CREATE TABLE t2_receptors AS
SELECT unique_id as gid, id, toid, postcode, geom
FROM s5a_receptors
ORDER BY gid ASC;
ALTER TABLE t2_receptors ADD PRIMARY KEY (gid);

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t3_best_receptors;
CREATE TABLE t3_best_receptors AS
SELECT id as gid, toid, postcode, near_road, road_mv, road_dist, geom
FROM s5c_best_receptor
ORDER BY gid ASC;
ALTER TABLE t3_best_receptors ADD PRIMARY KEY (gid);

DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t3_quite_receptors;
CREATE TABLE t3_quite_receptors AS
SELECT id as gid, toid, postcode, near_road, road_mv, road_dist, geom
FROM s5d_quite_receptor
ORDER BY gid ASC;
ALTER TABLE t3_quite_receptors ADD PRIMARY KEY (gid);

```



```
-- Subset major roads
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t4_major_roads;
CREATE TABLE t4_major_roads AS
SELECT *
FROM s0_clipped_roads
WHERE minor = 0;
DROP INDEX IF EXISTS maj_rds;
CREATE INDEX maj_rds on t4_major_roads using gist(geom);

-- Subset minor roads
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS t5_minor_roads;
CREATE TABLE t5_minor_roads AS
SELECT *
FROM s0_clipped_roads
WHERE minor = 1;
DROP INDEX IF EXISTS min_rds;
CREATE INDEX min_rds on t5_minor_roads using gist(geom);

-- Tidy: remove intermediate tables
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS s1_receptor_buildings, s2_building_lines, s3_all_points, s4_valid_points, s5a_receptors, s5b_selection_method,
s5c_best_receptor, s0_clipped_roads, road_classification, road_priority, s5c_quite_receptor, s5d_quite_receptor;
```


11.2 PostgreSQL: CNOSSOS-EU road traffic noise model functions

```

-- #####
-- ## Title: CNOSSOS-EU ROAD TRAFFIC NOISE MODEL (ADAPTED FROM THE BIOSHARE PROJECT)
-- ## Version: 1.4
-- ## Date: 20/02/2020
-- #####

-- #####
-- ## Version 1.4 (19th February 2020: Calvin Jephcote)
-- ## a. Reordered by function requirement and added some additional annotations.
-- ## b. Added the ability to drop types, if they already exist in the database (found in Part 1).
-- ## c. The function "ST_Line_Interpolate_Point" is now deprecated, and was replaced by "ST_LineInterpolatePoint"
-- ## d. Major and minor roads are now modelled as separate components by the wrapper functions
-- ##    "csharp_loop_mimic_major" and "csharp_loop_mimic".
-- ## e. These replace the wrapper function "csharp_loop_mimic" found in previous versions.
-- ## f. The wrapper functions "csharp_loop_mimic_major" and "csharp_loop_mimic", are now interactive and
-- ##    allow the user to define data inputs.
-- ## g. The model is now ran separately for major and minor road networks, the previously assumed "minorflow"
-- ##    distributions are now set to a value of 1 for all hours of the day.
-- ## h. Revised the models search radius: Major road-network model set to a 500m buffer, minor road-network model set to 100m.
-- ## i. Revised the "OS MasterMap g coefficients" function to be based on height rather than classification.
-- ## j. Anything land-cover feature less than 4.5m in height is provided with a coefficient of 1.
-- ## k. Changed one instance in script above from "get_coefgg(mm.legend)" to "get_coefgg(mm.hgt)".
-- ## l. Revised the "Bulk Nearest Neighbouring feature" search function (nnid), which now uses parallel processing.
-- ##
-- ## Version 1.3 (6th March 2018: John Gulliver)
-- ## a. Added script annotations.
-- ## b. Some minor revisions.
-- ##
-- ## Version 1.2 (18th April 2016: David Morley)
-- ## a. For full details please see Environmental Pollution (2015), pp.332-341 DOI information: 10.1016/j.envpol.2015.07.031
-- ## b. This is a version of the CNOSSOS-EU model as used in the above paper to make predictions for 'Model B.
-- ## c. It uses high-resolution land cover data rather than CORINE land cover (CLC), therefore
-- ##    it does not buffer around the road network.
-- #####

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-- #####

-- #####
-- ##### PART 1: Establish the structure of the output tables produced by the functions within this script.
-- ##### This is achieved by the registering a new data "type" for use in the current database.
-- ##### Warning: Removal of these created "types" will prevent any dependent function from running correctly.
-- #####

-- ## Return type for single path noise
DROP TYPE IF EXISTS llt_octave CASCADE;
create type llt_octave as (
    llt63 double precision,
    llt125 double precision,
    llt250 double precision,
    llt500 double precision,
    llt1000 double precision,
    llt2000 double precision,
    llt4000 double precision,
    llt8000 double precision
);

```



```

-- ## Return type for segment angle and distance
DROP TYPE IF EXISTS segtri CASCADE;
create type segtri as (
    theta double precision, --angle of view
    rmin double precision --perpendicular dist
);

-- ## Return type for traffic flow
DROP TYPE IF EXISTS qcat CASCADE;
create type qcat as (
    qcat1 double precision,
    qcat2 double precision,
    qcat3 double precision,
    qcat4a double precision,
    qcat4b double precision
);

-- ## Return type for traffic
DROP TYPE IF EXISTS vcat CASCADE;
create type vcat as (
    vcat1 double precision,
    vcat2 double precision,
    vcat3 double precision,
    vcat4a double precision,
    vcat4b double precision
);

-----
-- ### PART 2: Replacement sub-functions found in Version 1.4
-----

-- ## Revised function for identifying the nearest neighbouring feature.
-- ## (i.e. The nearest neighbouring feature function, can identify which road link is closest to each receptor point,
-- ## and return the unique identification number ("gid") of said road link)

create or replace function
nnid(inFeature      geometry
    , nearThings    text
    , nearThingsIdField text)
returns integer as $$
declare
sql text;
result integer;
begin
sql := ' SELECT nearest.' || quote_ident(nearThingsIdField)
    || ' FROM ' || quote_ident(nearThings) || ' AS features'
    || ' CROSS JOIN LATERAL (SELECT ' || quote_ident(nearThingsIdField)
    || ' FROM ' || quote_ident(nearThings) || ' AS near_features'
    || ' ORDER BY near_features.geom <-> $1'
    || ' LIMIT 1) AS nearest';
execute sql into result using inFeature;
return result;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Revised function for determining the "OS MasterMap g-coefficient"
-- ## Based on height rather than classification (anything less than 4.5m provided with a coefficient of 1)

create or replace function get_coeffg(mm_height double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    g double precision;
begin
    CASE WHEN mm_height >= 4.5 THEN g := 0;
    else
        g := 1;
    end case;
    return g;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- #####
-- #### PART 3: Import additional sub-functions
-- #####

-- ## Function to sum and apply a-weighting over octaves

create or replace function get_hourlydba(h integer, avtau double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    dba double precision;
    hq double precision;
    q double precision;
begin
    with octaves as (
        select
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt63)) as ltot63, --vi-10
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt125)) as ltot125,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt250)) as ltot250,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt500)) as ltot500,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt1000)) as ltot1000,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt2000)) as ltot2000,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt4000)) as ltot4000,
            10 * log(sum((p.octaves).lt8000)) as ltot8000
        from pths as p
        where p.hr = h
    )
    select coalesce(get_dba(array[o.ltot63, o.ltot125, o.ltot250, o.ltot500,
    o.ltot1000, o.ltot2000, o.ltot4000, o.ltot8000]), 0)
    from octaves as o into dba;
    --minor road correction
    select flow from minorflow where hour = h into hq;
    if hq < 1 then
        q := 1;
    else
        q := hq;
    end if;
    dba := incoherentsum((0.0432 * (20 - coalesce(avtau, 0)) + ((4.3429 * ln(q) + 34.581)), coalesce(dba, 0));
    return dba;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Function to get the incoherent sum of 2 noise values

create or replace function incoherentsum(a double precision, b double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    v double precision;
begin
    v := 10 * log(((10 ^ (a / 10)) + ((10 ^ (b / 10)))));
    return v;
end;
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

create or replace function get_traffic(rid integer, hr integer, roads text)
returns qcat as $$
declare
    q qcat;
    c1 double precision;
    c2 double precision;
    c3 double precision;
    c4a double precision;
    c4b double precision;
begin
    execute 'select (r.c1 / 100) * r.p' || hr || ' from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c1;
    execute 'select (r.c2 / 100) * r.p' || hr || ' from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c2;
    execute 'select (r.c3 / 100) * r.p' || hr || ' from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c3;
    execute 'select (r.c4a / 100) * r.p' || hr || ' from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c4a;
    execute 'select (r.c4b / 100) * r.p' || hr || ' from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c4b;
    q := (c1, c2, c3, c4a, c4b);
    return q;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

create or replace function get_speed(rid integer, roads text)
returns vcat as $$
declare
    v vcat;
    c1 double precision;
    c2 double precision;
    c3 double precision;
    c4a double precision;
    c4b double precision;
begin
    execute 'select r.speed1 from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c1;
    execute 'select r.speed2 from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c2;
    execute 'select r.speed3 from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c3;
    execute 'select r.speed4a from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c4a;
    execute 'select r.speed4b from ' || roads || ' as r where r.gid = ' || rid into c4b;
    v := (c1, c2, c3, c4a, c4b);
    return v;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to return the noise level calculations for one ray path

create or replace function get_noise(
q_0 qcat,
q_1 qcat,
q_2 qcat,
q_3 qcat,
q_4 qcat,
q_5 qcat,
q_6 qcat,
q_7 qcat,
q_8 qcat,

```



```

q_9 qcat,
q_10 qcat,
q_11 qcat,
q_12 qcat,
q_13 qcat,
q_14 qcat,
q_15 qcat,
q_16 qcat,
q_17 qcat,
q_18 qcat,
q_19 qcat,
q_20 qcat,
q_21 qcat,
q_22 qcat,
q_23 qcat,
speed vcat,
aov segtri, avh double precision, d double precision, fdso double precision, fdor double precision,
g double precision, tau double precision, gor double precision, gso double precision, p double precision)
returns void as $$
declare
    zs double precision := 0.05; --equivalent source height(m) (iii-1.2)
    zr double precision := 4; --equivalent receiver height(m) (viii-1.2)
    fm double precision[] := array[63, 125, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, 8000]; --octave band centres (hz)
    lamda double precision[] := array[5.4444, 2.744, 1.372, 0.686, 0.343, 0.1715, 0.08575, 0.042875]; --wavelength (m) at band
centres
    alphaatm double precision[] := array[0.105, 0.376, 1.124, 2.358, 4.079, 8.777, 26.607, 94.961]; --iso 9613-1
    kk double precision; --in vi-15
    adiv double precision; --geometrical divergence
    aatm double precision; --atmospheric absorbtion
    aboundaryh double precision; --vi-15
    aboundaryf double precision; --vi-15
    cf double precision; --in vi-16
    w double precision; --in vi-17
    llt double precision[8]; --long term sound level vi-9
    bheight boolean; --if ray intersects building height layer, and height >= 0.5m
    dif double precision[3]; --diffraction [s r, image s r, s image r]
    deltaf double precision[3]; --path difference under diffraction favourable [s r, image s r, s image r]
    deltah double precision[3]; --path difference under diffraction homogenous [s r, image s r, s image r]
    ch double precision; --height, diffraction
    mdc double precision; --c" multiple diffractions correction
    dso double precision; --distance from s to top of o
    dor double precision; --distance from top of o to r
    dsoi double precision; --distance from image s to top of o
    dori double precision; --distance from top of o to image r
    agroundso double precision; --ground attenuation s o
    agroundor double precision; --ground attenuation o r
    gwm double precision; --g'path or gpath to use
    lf_oct double precision[8];
    lh_oct double precision[8];
begin
    --find any type 1 diffractions
    if avh is not null and avh > 0.5 then
        --use building diffraction
        bheight := true;
        dso := sqrt(fdso ^ 2 + (avh - zs) ^ 2);
        dor := sqrt(fdor ^ 2 + (avh - zr) ^ 2);
        dsoi := sqrt(fdso ^ 2 + (avh + zs) ^ 2);
        dori := sqrt(fdor ^ 2 + (avh + zr) ^ 2);
        deltah[1] := dso + dor - d;
        deltah[2] := dsoi + dor - d;
        deltah[3] := dso + dori - d;
        deltaf[1] := get_curve(dso) + get_curve(dor) - get_curve(d);
        deltaf[2] := get_curve(dsoi) + get_curve(dor) - get_curve(d);
        deltaf[3] := get_curve(dso) + get_curve(dori) - get_curve(d);
    else
        --path has no urban area
        bheight := false;
        if d <= (30 * (zs + zr)) then

```



```

        gwm := get_gpath(g, d, zs, zr); --vi-14
    else
        gwm := g;
    end if;
end if;

--geometrical divergence
adiv := -10 * log((aov.theta) / (4 * pi() * aov.rmin)); --v-3b [in draft]
--adiv := 20 * log(d) + 11;

--boundary conditions
for i in 2..7 loop
    --calculations on elementary path
    aatm := alphaatm[i] * d / 1000; --vi-13
    kk := (2 * pi() * fm[i]) / 340; --vi-15

    if not bheight then
        --ground effect with no buildings
        w := get_w(gwm, fm[i]);
        cf := get_cf(w, d);
        --attenuation, homogenous conditions
        aboundaryh := get_agroundh(gwm, g, d, kk, cf, zs, zr);
        --attenuation, favourable conditions
        aboundaryf := get_agroundf(gwm, g, d, kk, cf, zs, zr);
    else
        --ground effect with building diffraction
        mdc := 1;
        ch := (fm[i] * avh) / 250.0; --vi-22
        ch := least(ch, 1);

        gwm := get_gpath(gso, dso, zs, avh);
        --homogenous path difference vi44c1
        dif := get_dif(lamda[i], mdc, delta, ch);
        w := get_w(gwm, fm[i]);
        cf := get_cf(w, dso);
        agroundso := get_agroundh(gwm, gso, dso, kk, cf, zs, avh);
        w := get_w(gor, fm[i]);
        cf := get_cf(w, dor);
        agroundor := get_agroundh(gor, gor, dor, kk, cf, avh, zr);
        aboundaryh := get_adif(dif, agroundso, agroundor);
        --favourable path difference vi44c2
        dif := get_dif(lamda[i], mdc, delta, ch);
        w := get_w(gso, fm[i]);
        cf := get_cf(w, dso);
        agroundso := get_agroundf(gwm, gso, dso, kk, cf, zs, avh);
        w := get_w(gor, fm[i]);
        cf := get_cf(w, dor);
        agroundor := get_agroundf(gor, gor, dor, kk, cf, avh, zr);
        aboundaryf := get_adif(dif, agroundso, agroundor); --vi-30, 31, 32
    end if;

    --attenuated sound levels, different conditions
    lf_oct[i] := (adiv + aatm + aboundaryf); --vi-5,6 lw - lf_oct[i]
    lh_oct[i] := (adiv + aatm + aboundaryh); --vi-7,8

end loop;

--for each hour and each octave
insert into pths select 0, get_sound(q_0, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 1, get_sound(q_1, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 2, get_sound(q_2, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 3, get_sound(q_3, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 4, get_sound(q_4, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 5, get_sound(q_5, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 6, get_sound(q_6, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 7, get_sound(q_7, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 8, get_sound(q_8, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 9, get_sound(q_9, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);

```



```

insert into pths select 10, get_sound(q_10, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 11, get_sound(q_11, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 12, get_sound(q_12, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 13, get_sound(q_13, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 14, get_sound(q_14, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 15, get_sound(q_15, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 16, get_sound(q_16, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 17, get_sound(q_17, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 18, get_sound(q_18, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 19, get_sound(q_19, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 20, get_sound(q_20, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 21, get_sound(q_21, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 22, get_sound(q_22, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);
insert into pths select 23, get_sound(q_23, speed, tau, p, lf_oct, lh_oct);

end
$$ language 'plpgsql' volatile;

-- ## Function to find the sound power level at source before attenuation

create or replace function get_sound(
q qcat, speed vcat,
tau double precision, p double precision,
lf_oct double precision[], lh_oct double precision[])
returns llt_octave as $$
declare
    llt double precision[8];
    tmp double precision; --air temperature correction
    k double precision[] := array[0.08, 0.04, 0.04, 0, 0]; --air temp correction
    vm double precision; --velocity from roadtype
    q double precision; --traffic flow
    lwp double precision; --individual propulsion noise
    lwr double precision; --individual rolling noise

    --rolling a
    ar double precision[][] := array[
        [79.7, 85.7, 84.5, 90.2, 97.3, 93.9, 84.1, 74.3],
        [84, 88.7, 91.5, 96.7, 97.4, 90.9, 83.8, 80.5],
        [87.0, 91.7, 94.1, 100.7, 100.8, 94.3, 87.1, 82.5],
        [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0],
        [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]];

    --propulsion a
    ap double precision[][] := array[
        [94.5, 89.2, 88.0, 85.9, 84.2, 86.9, 83.3, 76.1],
        [101, 96.5, 98.8, 96.8, 98.6, 95.2, 88.8, 82.7],
        [104.4, 100.6, 101.7, 101.0, 100.1, 95.9, 91.3, 85.3],
        [88, 87.5, 89.5, 93.7, 96.6, 98.8, 93.9, 88.7],
        [95, 97.2, 92.7, 92.9, 94.7, 93.2, 90.1, 86.5]];

    -- rolling b
    br double precision[][] := array[
        [30.0, 41.5, 38.9, 25.7, 32.5, 37.2, 39.0, 40.0],
        [30, 35.8, 32.6, 23.8, 30.1, 36.2, 38.3, 40.1],
        [30.0, 33.5, 31.3, 25.4, 31.8, 37.1, 38.6, 40.6],
        [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0],
        [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]];

    --propulsion b
    bp double precision[][] := array[
        [-1.3, 7.2, 7.7, 8.0, 8.0, 8.0, 8.0, 8.0],
        [-1.9, 4.7, 6.4, 6.5, 6.5, 6.5, 6.5, 6.5],
        [0.0, 3.0, 4.6, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0],
        [4.2, 7.4, 9.8, 11.6, 15.7, 18.9, 20.3, 20.6],
        [3.2, 5.9, 11.9, 11.6, 11.5, 12.6, 11.1, 12]];

    vref double precision := 70.0; --velocity constant
    lwm double precision[5]; --category source noise level

```



```

lwpr double precision; --combined rolling and propulsion
lw double precision; --combined categories source noise level
outllt llt_octave; --(return) 8x octaves at r before sum
lh double precision; --sound level in homogenous
lf double precision; --sound level in favourable

begin
  --for each octave
  for i in 2..7 loop
    --for vehicle categories
    --cat 1: light motor vehicles
    --cat 2: medium heavy vehicles
    --cat 3: heavy vehicles
    --cat 4a: powered-two-wheelers (<= 50cc)
    --cat 4b: powered-two-wheelers (> 50cc)
    for m in 1..5 loop
      --air temp correction
      tmp := k[m] * (20 - tau); --iii-10

      --speed, flow for road, vehicle class
      if m = 1 then
        vm := speed.vcat1;
        q := q.qcat1;
      elsif m = 2 then
        vm := speed.vcat2;
        q := q.qcat2;
      elsif m = 3 then
        vm := speed.vcat3;
        q := q.qcat3;
      elsif m = 4 then
        vm := speed.vcat4a;
        q := q.qcat4a;
      elsif m = 5 then
        vm := speed.vcat4b;
        q := q.qcat4b;
      end if;

      --
      raise notice 'vm: %   q: %', vm, q;

      if q is not null and q >= 0.5 then
        --individual vehicle noise
        lwr := ar[m][i] + br[m][i] * log(vm / vref) + tmp; --iii-5
        lwpr := ap[m][i] + bp[m][i] * ((vm - vref) / vref); --iii-11
        lwpr := 10 * log((10 ^ (lwr / 10)) + (10 ^ (lwpr / 10))); --iii-3
        --segment flow combined noise per vehicle category
        lwm[m] := lwpr + 10 * log(q / (1000 * vm)); --iii-1
      else
        lwm[m] := 0;
      end if;
    end loop;

    --combined all vehicle sources at s
    lw := 10 * log( (10 ^ (lwm[1] / 10)) + (10 ^ (lwm[2] / 10)) + (10 ^ (lwm[3] / 10)) + (10 ^ (lwm[4] / 10)) + (10 ^ (lwm[5]
/ 10)));

    lf := lw - greatest(lf_oct[i], 0);
    lh := lw - greatest(lh_oct[i], 0);

    --integrated long term sound level for path sr per octave
    llt[i] := 10 * log((p * (10 ^ (lf / 10))) + ((1 - p) * (10 ^ (lh / 10)))); --vi-9
  end loop;

  outllt := (get_lgt(llt[1]), get_lgt(llt[2]), get_lgt(llt[3]), get_lgt(llt[4]),
get_lgt(llt[5]), get_lgt(llt[6]), get_lgt(llt[7]), get_lgt(llt[8]));
  return outllt;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Function to find the air temperature at source

create or replace function get_temperature(r geometry, stations text, b integer)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    tau double precision;
    nn integer;
begin
    if b = 0 then
        return cast(stations as double precision);
    else
        nn := nnid(r, stations, 'src_id');
        execute '
select w.air_temp from ' || stations || ' as w
where w.src_id = ' || nn into tau;
        return tau;
    end if;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get the probability of favourable conditions for path

create or replace function get_favourable(rp geometry, stations text, b integer)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    p double precision;
    az double precision;
    d varchar;
    s geometry;
    nn integer;
begin
    if b = 0 then
        return cast(stations as double precision);
    else
        s := st_endpoint(rp);
        az := degrees(st_azimuth(st_startpoint(rp), s));
        if az >= 0 and az < 90 then
            d := 'ne';
        elsif az >= 90 and az < 180 then
            d := 'se';
        elsif az >= 180 and az < 270 then
            d := 'sw';
        else
            d := 'nw';
        end if;
        nn := nnid(s, stations, 'src_id');
        execute 'select w.' || d || ' from ' || stations || ' as w where w.src_id = ' || nn
into p;
        return p;
    end if;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Function to get the corrected g path, vi-14

create or replace function get_gpath(g double precision, d double precision,
zs double precision, zr double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    gpath double precision;
    gs double precision := 0; --ground effect at source (road)
begin
    gpath := (g * (d / (30 * (zs + zr)))) + (gs * (1 - (d / (30 * (zs + zr)))));
    return gpath;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get the curved ray path, vi-25,26

create or replace function get_curve(d double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    hat double precision;
    gamma double precision;
begin
    gamma := 8 * d;
    gamma := greatest(1000, gamma); --vi-24
    hat := (2 * gamma * asin(d / (2 * gamma)));
    return hat;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get adif, vi-30

create or replace function get_adif(dif double precision[3], agroundso double precision, agroundor double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    adif double precision;
begin
    adif := dif[1] + --vi-21
(-20 * log(1 + (((10 ^ (-agroundso / 20)) - 1) * (10 ^ (-(dif[2] - dif[1]) / 20)))))) + --vi-31
(-20 * log(1 + (((10 ^ (-agroundor / 20)) - 1) * (10 ^ (-(dif[3] - dif[1]) / 20)))))); --vi-32
    return adif;
    exception when invalid_argument_for_logarithm then
        return dif[1];
    end;
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Function to get pure diffraction, delta dif, vi-21

create or replace function get_dif(lamda double precision, mdc double precision,
delta double precision[3], ch double precision)
returns double precision[3] as $$
declare
    dif double precision[3];
begin
    for i in 1..3 loop
        if ((40 / lamda) * mdc * delta[i]) >= -2 then
            dif[i] := 10 * ch * log(3 + ((40 / lamda)) * mdc * delta[i]);
            if dif[i] < 0 then
                dif[i] := 0;
            end if;
            if i = 1 then
                dif[i] := least(dif[i], 25);
            end if;
        else
            dif[i] := 0;
        end if;
    end loop;
    return dif;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get cf for vi-16,17

create or replace function get_cf(w double precision, d double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    cf double precision;
begin
    cf := d * ((1 + (3 * w * d * exp(-sqrt(w * d)))) / (1 + (w * d)));
    return cf;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get aground favourable

create or replace function get_agroundf(g double precision, gpath double precision, d double precision,
kk double precision, cf double precision, zc double precision, zr double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    agroundf double precision;
    x double precision;
    zsc double precision;
    zrc double precision;
begin
    zsc := zs + (0.0002 * (((zs / (zs + zr)) ^ 2) * ((d ^ 2) / 2))) + (0.006 * (d / (zs + zr))); --vi-19
    zrc := zr + (0.0002 * (((zr / (zs + zr)) ^ 2) * ((d ^ 2) / 2))) + (0.006 * (d / (zs + zr)));
    if d <= 30 * (zsc + zrc) then --vi-20
        x := -3 * (1 - g);
    else
        x := (-3 * (1 - g)) * (1 + (2 * (1 - ((30 * (zsc + zrc)) / d))));
    end if;
    if gpath = 0 then
        agroundf := x;
    else
        agroundf := -10 * log((4 * (kk ^ 2) / (d ^ 2)) * ((zsc ^ 2) -
(sqrt(((2 * cf) / kk) * zsc) + (cf / kk)) *

```



```

        ((zrc ^ 2) - (sqrt(((2 * cf) / kk) * zrc) + (cf / kk))); --vi-15
        if agroundf < x then agroundf := x;
        end if;
    end if;
    return agroundf;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get aground homogenous

create or replace function get_agroundh(g double precision, gpath double precision, d double precision,
kk double precision, cf double precision, zs double precision, zr double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    agroundh double precision;
    x double precision;
begin
    if gpath = 0 then
        agroundh := -3;
    else
        agroundh := -10 * log((4 * (kk ^ 2) / (d ^ 2)) * ((zs ^ 2) -
(sqrt(((2 * cf) / kk) * zs) + (cf / kk)) *
(zr ^ 2) - (sqrt(((2 * cf) / kk) * zr) + (cf / kk))); --vi-15
        x := -3 * (1 - g);
        if agroundh < x then agroundh := x;
        end if;
    end if;
    return agroundh;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get w for vi-16,17

create or replace function get_w(g double precision, fm double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    w double precision;
begin
    w := 0.0185 * (((fm ^ 2.5) * (g ^ 2.6)) / (((fm ^ 1.5) * (g ^ 2.6)) +
(1300 * ((fm ^ 0.75) * (g ^ 1.3)))) + 1160000); --vi-17
    return w;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function used to log transform sound level

create or replace function get_lgt(lt double precision)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    t double precision;
begin
    t := 10 ^ (lt / 10);
    return t;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

```



```

-- ## Function to integrate octave band totals to final dba level

create or replace function get_dba(lt double precision[8])
returns double precision as $$
declare
    awc double precision[] := array[-26.22302364022129, -16.189851062139507, -8.675022287681816,
    -3.2479917598088837, 0, 1.2016993444284976, 0.9642291552357972, -1.144507424157968]; --iec 61672:2003
    t double precision;
begin
    t := 0;
    for i in 2..7 loop
        t := t + (10 ^ ((lt[i] + awc[i]) / 10));
    end loop;
    if t = 0 then
        return 0;
    end if;
    t := 10 * log(t);
    if t < 0 then
        t := 0;
    end if;
    return t; --vi-11 (is the final result)
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get the step ratio, used to divide a line into x.meter steps

create or replace function get_steprat(lgth double precision, x integer)
returns integer as $$
declare step integer;
begin
    if lgth < x then step := 100000;
    else step := cast(trunc(100000 / (lgth / x)) as integer);
    end if;
    return step;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- ## Function to get the angle of segment view from receptor, radians

create or replace function get_angleofview(r geometry, stt double precision,
    stp double precision, road geometry)
returns segtri as $$
declare
    triangle segtri;
    anglea double precision;
    angleb double precision;
    anglec double precision;
    pdist double precision;
    radist float;
    rbdist float;
    abdist float;
    a geometry;
    b geometry;
begin
    stp := least(stp, 100000); --snap to end of road
    a := ST_LineInterpolatePoint(road, stt / 100000);
    b := ST_LineInterpolatePoint(road, stp / 100000);
    abdist := st_distance(a, b);
    radist := st_distance(a, r);
    rbdist := st_distance(b, r);

```



```

--from crtn noise model
if abdist = 0 or radist = 0 or rbdist = 0 then
    anglea := 0;
    anglec := 0;
else
    anglea := (((rbdist ^ 2) - (radist ^ 2) - (abdist ^ 2)) / (-2 * radist * abdist));
    anglec := (((abdist ^ 2) - (radist ^ 2) - (rbdist ^ 2)) / (-2 * radist * rbdist));
end if;
if anglea > 1 or anglea < -1 then
    anglea := 0;
else
    anglea := acos(anglea);
end if;
if anglec > 1 or anglec < -1 then
    anglec := 0;
else
    anglec := acos(anglec);
end if;
angleb := pi() - anglea - anglec;
if anglea = pi() / 2 then
    pdist := radist;
elseif angleb = pi() / 2 then
    pdist := rbdist;
elseif anglea = pi() and angleb = 0 then
    pdist := 3.5;
    anglec := radians(1);
elseif anglea = 0 and angleb = pi() then
    pdist := 3.5;
    anglec := radians(1);
elseif anglea = 0 and angleb = 0 then
    pdist := 3.5;
    anglec := 2 * pi();
elseif anglea > pi() / 2 and anglea < pi() then
    pdist := sin(pi() - anglea) * radist;
elseif angleb > pi() / 2 and angleb < pi() then
    pdist := sin(pi() - angleb) * rbdist;
elseif anglea < pi() / 2 and angleb < pi() / 2 then
    pdist := sin(anglea) * radist;
end if;
if anglec = 0 then
    anglec = radians(0.00001);
end if;
if pdist = 0 then
    pdist = 3.5;
end if;
triangle := (anglec, pdist);
return triangle;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- #####
-- ##### PART 4: CNOSSOS-EU noise estimation function
-- #####

create or replace function cnosos_3(
    i integer,
    receptors text,
    roads text,
    landcover text,
    mettemp text,
    metwind text,
    radius double precision,
    seg_dst integer
)
returns double precision as $$

```



```

declare
  cwind integer;
  ctemp integer;
  db double precision;
  mtau double precision;

begin
  --get receptor
  execute 'insert into s
select gid, geom from ' || receptors || '
where gid = ' || i;

  --construct rays and road segments
  execute 'insert into temp_rays
with line as (
  --clip roads within 500m of r
  with rds as (
    select distinct rr.gid, rr.geom as recpt, t.gid as road_id,
    (st_dump(t.geom)).geom as road, get_steprat(st_length(t.geom), ' || seg_dst || ') as step_rat
    from s as rr inner join ' || roads || ' as t
    on st_dwithin(rr.geom, t.geom, ' || radius || ')
  )
  select * from rds
  union all
  --if no roads found in 500m of r, take the next nearest road
  select distinct rr.gid, rr.geom as recpt, t.gid as road_id,
  (st_dump(t.geom)).geom as road, get_steprat(st_length(t.geom), ' || seg_dst || ') as step_rat
  from ' || roads || ' as t, s as rr left join rds
  on rds.gid = rr.gid
  where rds.gid is null
  and t.gid = nnid(rr.geom, ' || roads || ', "gid")
)
select splt.gid, splt.road, splt.ray_step, splt.road_id,
st_makeline(splt.recpt, ST_LineInterpolatePoint(splt.road, cast(ray_step as double precision) / 100000)) as main_ray_path,
(cast(ray_step as double precision) / (cast(step_rat as double precision))) * cast(step_rat as double precision) as seg_start,
(cast(ray_step as double precision) / (cast(step_rat as double precision))) * cast(step_rat as double precision) + cast(step_rat
as double precision) as seg_end
from (
  select line.gid, line.recpt, line.step_rat, line.road, line.road_id,
  generate_series(line.step_rat / 2, 100000, line.step_rat) as ray_step
  from line
) as splt';

  --clip rays to 500m
  execute 'delete from temp_rays using (
  select id from
  (select r.gid, r.id, st_length(r.main_ray_path) as len
  from temp_rays as r) as lengths
  left join
  (select every.gid, every.total, outside.longer from
  (select count(r1.main_ray_path) as total, r1.gid
  from temp_rays as r1
  group by r1.gid) as every
  left join
  (select count(r1.main_ray_path) as longer, r1.gid
  from temp_rays as r1
  where st_length(r1.main_ray_path) > ' || radius || '
  group by r1.gid) as outside
  on every.gid = outside.gid) as counts
  on lengths.gid = counts.gid
  where (len > ' || radius || ' and total != 1)
  --calculation limit stated as 2km
  or (len > 2000 and total = 1) ) as remove
  where remove.id = temp_rays.id';

  --get rays broken on landcover, g and building heights
  execute 'truncate ray_broken;
insert into ray_broken

```



```

select os.id, os.geom, os.totlen, os.mm_id, os.hgt, os.g,
st_length(os.geom) as shape_length,
st_distance(os.s, st_endpoint(os.geom)) as near_dist
from
(select r.id, st_endpoint(r.main_ray_path) as s, get_coeffg(mm.hgt) as g,
(st_dump(st_intersection(r.main_ray_path, mm.geom))).geom as geom,
mm.legend, mm.mm_id, mm.hgt, st_length(r.main_ray_path) as totlen
from temp_rays as r, '|| landcover ||' as mm
where st_intersects(r.main_ray_path, mm.geom)) as os';

--using met data?
execute '
select count(relname) from pg_class
where relname = '"" || mettemp || ""'
into ctemp;
execute '
select count(relname) from pg_class
where relname = '"" || metwind || ""'
into cwind;

--ray_details
execute 'insert into ray_details
select g.gid, g.gpath, bar.gso, bar.gor, bar.dso, bar.dor, bar.hgt, aov.aov, met.tau, met.p, met.d, met.road_id
from
(select r.gid, sum(r.g * r.shape_length) / r.totlen as gpath
from ray_broken as r
group by r.gid, r.totlen) as g
left join
(with t as (
select dst.gid, dst.dso, dst.dor, dst.hgt, r.shape_length, r.near_dist, r.g, r.totlen, r.g * r.shape_length as dg
from ray_broken as r left join
(select a.totlen - (a.near_dist + (a.shape_length / 2)) as dor, a.near_dist + (a.shape_length / 2) as dso,
a.gid, a.totlen, a.hgt, a.geom
from
(select distinct on (r.gid) r.gid, r.hgt, r.geom,
r.mm_id, r.shape_length, r.near_dist, r.totlen
from ray_broken as r
order by r.gid, r.hgt desc) as a) as dst
on r.gid = dst.gid
)
select source_side.gid, source_side.gso, receipt_side.gor, source_side.dso, receipt_side.dor, source_side.hgt
from
(select t.gid, sum(t.dg) / sum(t.shape_length) as gso, t.dso, t.hgt
from t
where t.near_dist < t.dso
and t.hgt > 0.5
group by t.gid, t.dso, t.hgt) as source_side
left join
(select t.gid, sum(t.dg) / sum(t.shape_length) as gor, t.dor
from t
where t.near_dist > t.dso
and t.hgt > 0.5
group by t.gid, t.dor) as receipt_side
on receipt_side.gid = source_side.gid) as bar
on g.gid = bar.gid
left join
(select r.id, get_angleofview(st_startpoint(r.main_ray_path), r.seg_start, r.seg_end, r.road) as aov
from temp_rays as r) as aov
on aov.id = g.gid
left join
(select ray.id, st_length(ray.main_ray_path) as d, get_temperature(ray.main_ray_path, '"" || mettemp || ""', '||
ctemp ||') as tau,
get_favourable(ray.main_ray_path, '"" || metwind || ""', '|| cwind ||') as p, ray.road_id
from temp_rays as ray) as met
on g.gid = met.id';

--make calculations for each hour
execute 'select get_noise(

```



```

get_traffic(r.road_id, 0, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 1, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 2, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 3, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 4, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 5, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 6, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 7, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 8, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 9, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 10, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 11, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 12, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 13, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 14, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 15, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 16, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 17, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 18, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 19, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 20, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 21, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 22, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 23, "" || roads || ""'),
get_speed(r.road_id, "" || roads || ""'),
r.aov, r.hgt, r.d, r.dso,
r.dor, coalesce(r.g, 0), r.tau, coalesce(r.gor, 0), coalesce(r.gso, 0), r.p) as lrt
from ray_details as r';

--temperature for minor correction
select avg(r.tau) from ray_details as r into mtau;
--if cannot get ray average use receptor site
if mtau is null then
    mtau := 11.0;
end if;

--save to results table
insert into tempout
with hourly as (
    select
        get_hourlydba(0, mtau) as laeq1h_0,
        get_hourlydba(1, mtau) as laeq1h_1,
        get_hourlydba(2, mtau) as laeq1h_2,
        get_hourlydba(3, mtau) as laeq1h_3,
        get_hourlydba(4, mtau) as laeq1h_4,
        get_hourlydba(5, mtau) as laeq1h_5,
        get_hourlydba(6, mtau) as laeq1h_6,
        get_hourlydba(7, mtau) as laeq1h_7,
        get_hourlydba(8, mtau) as laeq1h_8,
        get_hourlydba(9, mtau) as laeq1h_9,
        get_hourlydba(10, mtau) as laeq1h_10,
        get_hourlydba(11, mtau) as laeq1h_11,
        get_hourlydba(12, mtau) as laeq1h_12,
        get_hourlydba(13, mtau) as laeq1h_13,
        get_hourlydba(14, mtau) as laeq1h_14,
        get_hourlydba(15, mtau) as laeq1h_15,
        get_hourlydba(16, mtau) as laeq1h_16,
        get_hourlydba(17, mtau) as laeq1h_17,
        get_hourlydba(18, mtau) as laeq1h_18,
        get_hourlydba(19, mtau) as laeq1h_19,
        get_hourlydba(20, mtau) as laeq1h_20,
        get_hourlydba(21, mtau) as laeq1h_21,
        get_hourlydba(22, mtau) as laeq1h_22,
        get_hourlydba(23, mtau) as laeq1h_23
    )
select s.gid,
--hourly predictions
laeq1h_0, laeq1h_1, laeq1h_2, laeq1h_3, laeq1h_4, laeq1h_5, laeq1h_6,

```



```

laeq1h_7, laeq1h_8, laeq1h_9, laeq1h_10, laeq1h_11, laeq1h_12,
laeq1h_13, laeq1h_14, laeq1h_15, laeq1h_16, laeq1h_17, laeq1h_18,
laeq1h_19, laeq1h_20, laeq1h_21, laeq1h_22, laeq1h_23,

--day
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 /
10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10)))) / 12) as lday,

--evening
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10)))) / 4) as leve,

--night
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_23 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_0 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_1 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_2 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_3 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_4 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_5 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_6 / 10)))) / 8) as lnight,

--laeq16
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 /
10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10)))) / 16) as laeq16,

--liden
10 * log(((12 * (10 ^ ((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10))
+ (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10)))) / 12)) / 12) + (4 * (10 ^ (((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10))
+ (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10)))) / 4) + 5) / 10))) +
(8 * (10 ^ (((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_23 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_0 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_1 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_2 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_3 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_4 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_5 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_6 / 10)))) / 8) + 10) / 10)))) / 24) as liden,

--coordinates
st_x(s.geom), st_y(s.geom)
from hourly, s;

--clear tables
truncate s;
truncate temp_rays;
truncate ray_broken;
truncate ray_details;
truncate pths;

--report progress
select t.laeq16 from tempout as t where gid = i into db;
return db;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' volatile;

```



```

-- #####
-- ##### PART 5: Wrapper functions, used to implement the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major or minor roads,
-- ##### based on user defined parameters. Previously, the CNOSSOS-EU noise model was implemented by the wrapper function
-- ##### "csharp_loop_mimic". In version 1.4, major and minor roads are modelled as separate components by the wrapper functions
-- ##### "csharp_loop_mimic_major" and "csharp_loop_mimic".
-- #####

-- ## Wrapper function, to model the noise contributions from major roads

create or replace function
csharp_loop_mimic_major(recpt          text
                        , roads        text
                        , landcover     text
                        , mettemp       text
                        , metwind       text)
returns void as $$
declare

    radius integer := 500; --road search buffer from receptor
    seg_dst integer := 20; --distance between each point on road

    nrow integer;
    result double precision;
    stt timestamp;
begin
    drop table if exists s;
    drop table if exists temp_rays;
    drop table if exists ray_broken;
    drop table if exists ray_details;
    drop table if exists pths;
    drop table if exists tempout;
    drop table if exists minorflow;

    --output table
    create table tempout (
        gid integer,
        laeq1h_0 double precision,
        laeq1h_1 double precision,
        laeq1h_2 double precision,
        laeq1h_3 double precision,
        laeq1h_4 double precision,
        laeq1h_5 double precision,
        laeq1h_6 double precision,
        laeq1h_7 double precision,
        laeq1h_8 double precision,
        laeq1h_9 double precision,
        laeq1h_10 double precision,
        laeq1h_11 double precision,
        laeq1h_12 double precision,
        laeq1h_13 double precision,
        laeq1h_14 double precision,
        laeq1h_15 double precision,
        laeq1h_16 double precision,
        laeq1h_17 double precision,
        laeq1h_18 double precision,
        laeq1h_19 double precision,
        laeq1h_20 double precision,
        laeq1h_21 double precision,
        laeq1h_22 double precision,
        laeq1h_23 double precision,
        lday double precision,
        leve double precision,
        Inight double precision,
        laeq16 double precision,
        lden double precision,
        st_x double precision,
        st_y double precision
    );

```



```

--temporary tables
create table s (
    gid integer,
    geom geometry
);
create table temp_rays (
    gid integer,
    road geometry,
    ray_step integer,
    road_id integer,
    main_ray_path geometry,
    seg_start double precision,
    seg_end double precision,
    id serial
);
create index temp1_indx on temp_rays using gist(main_ray_path);
create index temp2_indx on temp_rays using gist(road);
create table ray_broken (
    gid integer,
    geom geometry,
    totlen double precision,
    mm_id integer,
    hgt double precision,
    g double precision,
    shape_length double precision,
    near_dist double precision
);
create index ray_broken_indx on ray_broken using gist(geom);
create table ray_details (
    gid integer,
    g double precision,
    gso double precision,
    gor double precision,
    dso double precision,
    dor double precision,
    hgt double precision,
    aov segtri,
    tau double precision,
    p double precision,
    d double precision,
    road_id integer
);
create table pths (
    hr integer,
    octaves llt_octave
);
create table minorflow (
    hour double precision,
    flow double precision
);
--UK 600 per day
insert into minorflow values (0, 1);
insert into minorflow values (1, 1);
insert into minorflow values (2, 1);
insert into minorflow values (3, 1);
insert into minorflow values (4, 1);
insert into minorflow values (5, 1);
insert into minorflow values (6, 1);
insert into minorflow values (7, 1);
insert into minorflow values (8, 1);
insert into minorflow values (9, 1);
insert into minorflow values (10, 1);
insert into minorflow values (11, 1);
insert into minorflow values (12, 1);
insert into minorflow values (13, 1);
insert into minorflow values (14, 1);
insert into minorflow values (15, 1);

```



```

insert into minorflow values (16, 1);
insert into minorflow values (17, 1);
insert into minorflow values (18, 1);
insert into minorflow values (19, 1);
insert into minorflow values (20, 1);
insert into minorflow values (21, 1);
insert into minorflow values (22, 1);
insert into minorflow values (23, 1);

--do the calculations
execute 'select count(*) from ' || recpt into nrow;
for a in 1..nrow loop
    select clock_timestamp() into stt;
    select cnosos_3(a, recpt, roads,
landcover, mettemp, metwind,
radius, seg_dst) into result;
    raise notice '### % of %: laeq16 = %, time: % ###', a, nrow, result, clock_timestamp() - stt;
end loop;

--final table
drop table if exists output;
execute '
create table output as
select a.*,
laeq1h_0, laeq1h_1, laeq1h_2, laeq1h_3, laeq1h_4, laeq1h_5, laeq1h_6,
laeq1h_7, laeq1h_8, laeq1h_9, laeq1h_10, laeq1h_11, laeq1h_12, laeq1h_13,
laeq1h_14, laeq1h_15, laeq1h_16, laeq1h_17, laeq1h_18, laeq1h_19, laeq1h_20,
laeq1h_21, laeq1h_22, laeq1h_23, lday, leve, lnight, laeq16, lden,
b.st_x, b.st_y from ' || recpt || ' as a
left join tempout as b on a.gid = b.gid';
truncate tempout;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' volatile;

-- ## Wrapper function, to model the noise contributions from minor roads

create or replace function
csharp_loop_mimic_minor(recpt          text
                        , roads         text
                        , landcover     text
                        , mettemp      text
                        , metwind      text)
returns void as $$
declare
radius integer := 100; --road search buffer from receptor
seg_dst integer := 20; --distance between each point on road

nrow integer;
result double precision;
stt timestamp;
begin
drop table if exists s;
drop table if exists temp_rays;
drop table if exists ray_broken;
drop table if exists ray_details;
drop table if exists pths;
drop table if exists tempout;
drop table if exists minorflow;

--output table
create table tempout (
gid integer,
laeq1h_0 double precision,

```



```

    laeq1h_1 double precision,
    laeq1h_2 double precision,
    laeq1h_3 double precision,
    laeq1h_4 double precision,
    laeq1h_5 double precision,
    laeq1h_6 double precision,
    laeq1h_7 double precision,
    laeq1h_8 double precision,
    laeq1h_9 double precision,
    laeq1h_10 double precision,
    laeq1h_11 double precision,
    laeq1h_12 double precision,
    laeq1h_13 double precision,
    laeq1h_14 double precision,
    laeq1h_15 double precision,
    laeq1h_16 double precision,
    laeq1h_17 double precision,
    laeq1h_18 double precision,
    laeq1h_19 double precision,
    laeq1h_20 double precision,
    laeq1h_21 double precision,
    laeq1h_22 double precision,
    laeq1h_23 double precision,
    lday double precision,
    leve double precision,
    lnight double precision,
    laeq16 double precision,
    lden double precision,
    st_x double precision,
    st_y double precision
);

--temporary tables
create table s (
    gid integer,
    geom geometry
);
create table temp_rays (
    gid integer,
    road geometry,
    ray_step integer,
    road_id integer,
    main_ray_path geometry,
    seg_start double precision,
    seg_end double precision,
    id serial
);
create index temp1_idx on temp_rays using gist(main_ray_path);
create index temp2_idx on temp_rays using gist(road);
create table ray_broken (
    gid integer,
    geom geometry,
    totlen double precision,
    mm_id integer,
    hgt double precision,
    g double precision,
    shape_length double precision,
    near_dist double precision
);
create index ray_broken_idx on ray_broken using gist(geom);
create table ray_details (
    gid integer,
    g double precision,
    gso double precision,
    gor double precision,
    dso double precision,
    dor double precision,
    hgt double precision,

```



```

        aov segtri,
        tau double precision,
        p double precision,
        d double precision,
        road_id integer
    );
create table pths (
    hr integer,
    octaves llt_octave
);
create table minorflow (
    hour double precision,
    flow double precision
);
--UK 600 per day
insert into minorflow values (0, 1);
insert into minorflow values (1, 1);
insert into minorflow values (2, 1);
insert into minorflow values (3, 1);
insert into minorflow values (4, 1);
insert into minorflow values (5, 1);
insert into minorflow values (6, 1);
insert into minorflow values (7, 1);
insert into minorflow values (8, 1);
insert into minorflow values (9, 1);
insert into minorflow values (10, 1);
insert into minorflow values (11, 1);
insert into minorflow values (12, 1);
insert into minorflow values (13, 1);
insert into minorflow values (14, 1);
insert into minorflow values (15, 1);
insert into minorflow values (16, 1);
insert into minorflow values (17, 1);
insert into minorflow values (18, 1);
insert into minorflow values (19, 1);
insert into minorflow values (20, 1);
insert into minorflow values (21, 1);
insert into minorflow values (22, 1);
insert into minorflow values (23, 1);

--do the calculations
execute 'select count(*) from ' || rcpt into nrow;
for a in 1..nrow loop
    select clock_timestamp() into stt;
    select crosso3_3(a, rcpt, roads,
        landcover, mettemp, metwind,
        radius, seg_dst) into result;
    raise notice '### % of %: laeq16 = %, time: % ###', a, nrow, result, clock_timestamp() - stt;
end loop;

--final table
drop table if exists output;
execute '
create table output as
select a.*,
laeq1h_0, laeq1h_1, laeq1h_2, laeq1h_3, laeq1h_4, laeq1h_5, laeq1h_6,
laeq1h_7, laeq1h_8, laeq1h_9, laeq1h_10, laeq1h_11, laeq1h_12, laeq1h_13,
laeq1h_14, laeq1h_15, laeq1h_16, laeq1h_17, laeq1h_18, laeq1h_19, laeq1h_20,
laeq1h_21, laeq1h_22, laeq1h_23, lday, leve, lnight, laeq16, lden,
b.st_x, b.st_y from ' || rcpt || ' as a
left join tempout as b on a.gid = b.gid';
truncate tempout;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' volatile;
```


11.3 PostgreSQL: CNOSSOS-EU road traffic noise model functions (optional)

If the land cover has complete coverage and detailed classifications, then surface roughness coefficient values can be assigned in a more complex manner (see section 7.4).

```

-- #####
-- ## OS MasterMap g-coefficient function (01/10/2020)
-- #####

create or replace function get_coeffg_ver2(descriptivegroup varchar)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    g double precision;
    s text;
begin
    s := descriptivegroup;
    case s
        WHEN
            'General Surface',
            'General Surface,Historic Interest',
            'General Surface,Natural Environment',
            'Landform',
            'Landform,General Feature',
            'Landform,General Surface',
            'Landform,Historic Interest',
            'Natural Environment',
            'Natural Environment,General Surface',
            'Natural Environment,Historic Interest',
            'Natural Environment,Roadside',
            'Roadside,Natural Environment',
            'Unclassified'
        THEN
            g := 1;
        ELSE
            g := 0;
        end case;
    return g;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' stable;

-- #####
-- #### PART 4: CNOSSOS-EU noise estimation function
-- #### Changed one instance in script above from "get_coeffg(mm.hgt)" to "get_coeffg_ver2(mm.descriptivegroup)"
-- #####

create or replace function crosso3(
    i integer,
    receptors text,
    roads text,
    landcover text,
    mettemp text,
    metwind text,
    radius double precision,
    seg_dst integer
)
returns double precision as $$
declare
    cwind integer;
    ctemp integer;
    db double precision;
    mtau double precision;
begin
    --get receptor

```



```

execute 'insert into s
select gid, geom from ' || receptors || '
where gid = ' || i;

--construct rays and road segments
execute 'insert into temp_rays
with line as (
  --clip roads within 500m of r
  with rds as (
    select distinct rr.gid, rr.geom as recpt, t.gid as road_id,
    (st_dump(t.geom)).geom as road, get_steprat(st_length(t.geom), ' || seg_dst || ') as step_rat
    from s as rr inner join ' || roads || ' as t
    on st_dwithin(rr.geom, t.geom, ' || radius || ')
  )
  select * from rds
  union all
  --if no roads found in 500m of r, take the next nearest road
  select distinct rr.gid, rr.geom as recpt, t.gid as road_id,
  (st_dump(t.geom)).geom as road, get_steprat(st_length(t.geom), ' || seg_dst || ') as step_rat
  from ' || roads || ' as t, s as rr left join rds
  on rds.gid = rr.gid
  where rds.gid is null
  and t.gid = nnid(rr.geom, ' || roads || ', "gid")
)
select splt.gid, splt.road, splt.ray_step, splt.road_id,
st_makeline(splt.recpt, ST_LineInterpolatePoint(splt.road, cast(ray_step as double precision) / 100000)) as main_ray_path,
(cast(ray_step as double precision) / (cast(step_rat as double precision))) * cast(step_rat as double precision) as seg_start,
(cast(ray_step as double precision) / (cast(step_rat as double precision))) * cast(step_rat as double precision) + cast(step_rat
as double precision) as seg_end
from (
  select line.gid, line.recpt, line.step_rat, line.road, line.road_id,
  generate_series(line.step_rat / 2, 100000, line.step_rat) as ray_step
  from line
) as splt';

--clip rays to 500m
execute 'delete from temp_rays using (
  select id from
  (select r.gid, r.id, st_length(r.main_ray_path) as len
  from temp_rays as r) as lengths
  left join
  (select every.gid, every.total, outside.longer from
  (select count(r1.main_ray_path) as total, r1.gid
  from temp_rays as r1
  group by r1.gid) as every
  left join
  (select count(r1.main_ray_path) as longer, r1.gid
  from temp_rays as r1
  where st_length(r1.main_ray_path) > ' || radius || '
  group by r1.gid) as outside
  on every.gid = outside.gid) as counts
  on lengths.gid = counts.gid
  where (len > ' || radius || ' and total != 1)
  --calculation limit stated as 2km
  or (len > 2000 and total = 1) ) as remove
where remove.id = temp_rays.id';

--get rays broken on landcover, g and building heights
execute 'truncate ray_broken;
insert into ray_broken
select os.id, os.geom, os.totlen, os.mm_id, os.hgt, os.g,
st_length(os.geom) as shape_length,
st_distance(os.s, st_endpoint(os.geom)) as near_dist
from
(select r.id, st_endpoint(r.main_ray_path) as s, get_coeffg_ver2(mm.descriptivegroup) as g,
(st_dump(st_intersection(r.main_ray_path, mm.geom))).geom as geom,
mm.legend, mm.mm_id, mm.hgt, st_length(r.main_ray_path) as totlen

```



```

from temp_rays as r, '|| landcover ||' as mm
where st_intersects(r.main_ray_path, mm.geom) as os';

--using met data?
execute '
select count(relname) from pg_class
where relname = '|| mettemp ||'
into ctemp;
execute '
select count(relname) from pg_class
where relname = '|| metwind ||'
into cwind;

--ray_details
execute 'insert into ray_details
select g.gid, g.gpath, bar.gso, bar.gor, bar.dso, bar.dor, bar.hgt, aov.aov, met.tau, met.p, met.d, met.road_id
from
(select r.gid, sum(r.g * r.shape_length) / r.totlen as gpath
from ray_broken as r
group by r.gid, r.totlen) as g
left join
(with t as (
select dst.gid, dst.dso, dst.dor, dst.hgt, r.shape_length, r.near_dist, r.g, r.totlen, r.g * r.shape_length as dg
from ray_broken as r left join
(select a.totlen - (a.near_dist + (a.shape_length / 2)) as dor, a.near_dist + (a.shape_length / 2) as dso,
a.gid, a.totlen, a.hgt, a.geom
from
(select distinct on (r.gid) r.gid, r.hgt, r.geom,
r.mm_id, r.shape_length, r.near_dist, r.totlen
from ray_broken as r
order by r.gid, r.hgt desc) as a) as dst
on r.gid = dst.gid
)
select source_side.gid, source_side.gso, recept_side.gor, source_side.dso, recept_side.dor, source_side.hgt
from
(select t.gid, sum(t.dg) / sum(t.shape_length) as gso, t.dso, t.hgt
from t
where t.near_dist < t.dso
and t.hgt > 0.5
group by t.gid, t.dso, t.hgt) as source_side
left join
(select t.gid, sum(t.dg) / sum(t.shape_length) as gor, t.dor
from t
where t.near_dist > t.dso
and t.hgt > 0.5
group by t.gid, t.dor) as recept_side
on recept_side.gid = source_side.gid) as bar
on g.gid = bar.gid
left join
(select r.id, get_angleofview(st_startpoint(r.main_ray_path), r.seg_start, r.seg_end, r.road) as aov
from temp_rays as r) as aov
on aov.id = g.gid
left join
(select ray.id, st_length(ray.main_ray_path) as d, get_temperature(ray.main_ray_path, '|| mettemp ||', '||
ctemp ||') as tau,
get_favourable(ray.main_ray_path, '|| metwind ||', '|| cwind ||') as p, ray.road_id
from temp_rays as ray) as met
on g.gid = met.id';

--make calculations for each hour
execute 'select get_noise(
get_traffic(r.road_id, 0, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 1, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 2, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 3, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 4, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 5, '|| roads ||'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 6, '|| roads ||'),

```



```

get_traffic(r.road_id, 7, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 8, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 9, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 10, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 11, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 12, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 13, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 14, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 15, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 16, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 17, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 18, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 19, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 20, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 21, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 22, "" || roads || ""'),
get_traffic(r.road_id, 23, "" || roads || ""'),
get_speed(r.road_id, "" || roads || ""'),
r.aov, r.hgt, r.d, r.dso,
r.dor, coalesce(r.g, 0), r.tau, coalesce(r.gor, 0), coalesce(r.gso, 0), r.p) as llt
from ray_details as r';

--temperature for minor correction
select avg(r.tau) from ray_details as r into mtau;
--if cannot get ray average use receptor site
if mtau is null then
    mtau := 11.0;
end if;

--save to results table
insert into temptout
with hourly as (
    select
        get_hourlydba(0, mtau) as laeq1h_0,
        get_hourlydba(1, mtau) as laeq1h_1,
        get_hourlydba(2, mtau) as laeq1h_2,
        get_hourlydba(3, mtau) as laeq1h_3,
        get_hourlydba(4, mtau) as laeq1h_4,
        get_hourlydba(5, mtau) as laeq1h_5,
        get_hourlydba(6, mtau) as laeq1h_6,
        get_hourlydba(7, mtau) as laeq1h_7,
        get_hourlydba(8, mtau) as laeq1h_8,
        get_hourlydba(9, mtau) as laeq1h_9,
        get_hourlydba(10, mtau) as laeq1h_10,
        get_hourlydba(11, mtau) as laeq1h_11,
        get_hourlydba(12, mtau) as laeq1h_12,
        get_hourlydba(13, mtau) as laeq1h_13,
        get_hourlydba(14, mtau) as laeq1h_14,
        get_hourlydba(15, mtau) as laeq1h_15,
        get_hourlydba(16, mtau) as laeq1h_16,
        get_hourlydba(17, mtau) as laeq1h_17,
        get_hourlydba(18, mtau) as laeq1h_18,
        get_hourlydba(19, mtau) as laeq1h_19,
        get_hourlydba(20, mtau) as laeq1h_20,
        get_hourlydba(21, mtau) as laeq1h_21,
        get_hourlydba(22, mtau) as laeq1h_22,
        get_hourlydba(23, mtau) as laeq1h_23
    )
select s.gid,
--hourly predictions
laeq1h_0, laeq1h_1, laeq1h_2, laeq1h_3, laeq1h_4, laeq1h_5, laeq1h_6,
laeq1h_7, laeq1h_8, laeq1h_9, laeq1h_10, laeq1h_11, laeq1h_12,
laeq1h_13, laeq1h_14, laeq1h_15, laeq1h_16, laeq1h_17, laeq1h_18,
laeq1h_19, laeq1h_20, laeq1h_21, laeq1h_22, laeq1h_23,
--day
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 /
10)) +

```



```

(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10))) / 12) as lday,

--evening
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10))) / 4) as leve,

--night
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_23 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_0 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_1 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_2 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_3 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_4 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_5 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_6 / 10))) / 8) as lnight,

--laeq16
10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 /
10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10))) / 16) as laeq16,

--liden
10 * log(((12 * (10 ^ ((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_7 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_8 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_9 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_10 / 10))
+ (10 ^ (laeq1h_11 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_12 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_13 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_14 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_15 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_16 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_17 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_18 / 10))) / 12)) / 12) + (4 * (10 ^ ((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_19 / 10))
+ (10 ^ (laeq1h_20 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_21 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_22 / 10))) / 4) + 5) / 10))) +
(8 * (10 ^ (((10 * log(((10 ^ (laeq1h_23 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_0 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_1 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_2 / 10)) +
(10 ^ (laeq1h_3 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_4 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_5 / 10)) + (10 ^ (laeq1h_6 / 10))) / 8) + 10) / 10)))) / 24) as liden,

--coordinates
st_x(s.geom), st_y(s.geom)
from hourly, s;

--clear tables
truncate s;
truncate temp_rays;
truncate ray_broken;
truncate ray_details;
truncate pths;

--report progress
select t.laeq16 from tempout as t where gid = i into db;
return db;
end
$$ language 'plpgsql' volatile;

```

11.4 PostgreSQL: Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads (1)

```

-- #####
-- ##### Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads (maximum exposure)
-- #####

-- ##### Run the major road-network noise model for the maximum point of exposure on the receptor buildings

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_major('t3_best_receptors', 't4_major_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t6_noise_major_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

-- ##### Run the minor road-network noise model for the maximum point of exposure on the receptor buildings

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_minor('t3_best_receptors', 't5_minor_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t7_noise_minor_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

```


11.5 PostgreSQL: Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads (2)

```

-- #####
-- #### Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads (minimum exposure)
-- #####

-- #### Run the major road-network noise model for the quietest receptor points (QSIDE)

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_major('t3_best_receptors', 't4_major_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t6_noise_major_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

-- #### Run the minor road-network noise model for the quietest receptor points (QSIDE)

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_minor('t3_best_receptors', 't5_minor_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t7_noise_minor_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

```

11.6 PostgreSQL: Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads (3)

```

-- #####
-- #### Run the CNOSSOS-EU noise model for major and minor roads
-- #####

-- #### Run the major road-network noise model for all receptor points

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_major('t2_receptors', 't4_major_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t6_noise_major_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

-- #### Run the minor road-network noise model for all receptor points

SELECT csharp_loop_mimic_minor('t2_receptors', 't5_minor_roads', 'mm_landcover', 'met_temp_2013', 'met_wind_2013');
ALTER TABLE output RENAME TO t7_noise_minor_roads; -- Rename output table
DROP TABLE IF EXISTS minorflow, pths, ray_broken, ray_details, s, temp_rays, tempout; -- Delete intermediate tables

```

